

African Universities Performance Indicator Data

A MANUAL
on Collecting
Academic Programme,
Student and Academic Staff Data

Compiled by Ian Bunting

CHET

Centre for Higher Education Transformation (CHET)

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Disclaimer

Data were obtained directly from each of the eight universities participating in the HERANA project. The quality of the data presented in this report is therefore dependent to a large degree on the accuracy of the institutional data submissions. The data were supplied by the institutions and the formatted data tables were checked by the institutions on two separate occasions.

Institutions are welcome to submit to CHET further corrections and updates that may have become evident since the last checks made in 2013.

Acronyms and abbreviations

Botswana	University of Botswana
Dar es Salaam	University of Dar es Salaam (Tanzania)
Cape Town	University of Cape Town (South Africa)
CHET	Centre for Higher Education Transformation
Eduardo Mondlane	Eduardo Mondlane University (Mozambique)
FTE	Full-time equivalent
Ghana	University of Ghana
HEMIS	South Africa's Higher Education Management Information System
HERANA	Higher Education Research and Advocacy Network in Africa
Makerere	Makerere University (Uganda)
Mauritius	University of Mauritius
Nairobi	University of Nairobi (Kenya)
OECD	Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development
PQM	Programme and qualification mix
SET	Science, engineering and technology
US	United States of America

PART ONE

INTRODUCTION

1 Background: CHET and performance indicators

1.1 Performance indicators for South African universities

The background to this manual is CHET's research interests in indicators and the measuring of performance in South African higher education, which have been reported in the publications listed below:

- Cloete N & Bunting I (2000) *Higher Education Transformation: Assessing Performance in South Africa*. CHET: Pretoria
- Cloete N, Bunting L & Bunting I (2002) *Transformation Indicators Applied to Two South African Higher Education Institutions*. CHET Pretoria.
- Bunting I & Cloete N (2004) *Developing Performance Indicators for Higher Education: A South African Case Study*. CHET: Cape Town
- Bunting I, Sheppard C, Cloete N & Belding L (2010) *Performance Indicators: South African Higher Education 2000–2008*. CHET: Cape Town

CHET's reflections on the uses of indicators and performance measurement in South Africa stemmed from its broader interests in higher education governance – in particular, the governance model that had been adopted by South Africa in the post-apartheid era. South Africa's higher education governance model became, after 1997, one of state supervision rather than the apartheid mix of state control and market-driven models. A key feature of this state supervision model is that it permits higher education institutions to manage their own affairs within a framework of nationally determined objectives. These national objectives include, for example, goals related to total student enrolments in the system, and to the qualifications and fields of study that should be offered by the higher education system. The South African government uses enrolment and academic programme goals to steer the higher education system by (a) specifying enrolment targets for individual institutions, (b) determining what qualifications and fields of study they can offer, (c) linking these goals to a funding system that contains performance incentives, and (d) monitoring institutional performance in relation to these goals and incentives.

CHET extracted from its analyses of this state supervision model what it took to be the three essential ingredients of a higher education performance measurement system. These are the availability of:

- government goals for the higher education system;
- government targets for individual universities; and
- quantitative data on the academic functioning of universities.

The data required for the various South African performance indicator analyses were reasonably easy to find. Government goals for the university system were extracted from the 1997 White Paper *A Programme for the Transformation of Higher Education*, and the 2001 *National Plan for Higher Education*. Targets for individual universities were published after 2004 in *Ministerial Statements on Student Enrolment Planning* and in *Ministerial Statements on Higher Education Funding*. Quantitative data on students and staff were extracted from data that each university submitted annually to the national Department of Higher Education's higher education management information system (HEMIS). Research publication data were extracted from the returns submitted annually by each university in terms of the requirements of the government funding framework.

1.2 Cross-national performance indicators: CHET's initial project

In 2007 CHET decided to extend its work on performance indicators to determine if sets of indicators could be applied across a range of African countries. The first report on cross-national performance measurement was published by CHET in 2012. (See Bunting I & Cloete N (2012) *Cross-national Performance Indicators: A Case Study of Eight African Countries*. CHET: Cape Town.) In this report CHET indicated that it acknowledged that the first two elements in South Africa's performance management system might not be applicable to universities in other countries, which have different governance systems, different national higher education policies and different sets of targets for their universities. CHET maintained, however, that the key principle of performance being relative to goals would have to remain in place, and that any cross-national system would have to identify sets of goals that could apply to all universities involved.

The 2012 report argued that this principle could be satisfied if the most prominent (or flagship) university in a range of countries is identified, if the goals built into the mission and vision statements of each flagship university are extracted, and if these are then related to goals that should be embedded in their academic cores. The report describes this academic core as the inputs available for the delivery of teaching and research, and the research and teaching outputs that the university produces on basis of these inputs. CHET concluded in the report that the cross-national measurement of the performance of universities could be based on assessments of the extent to which they have satisfied the goals embedded in their academic cores.

The eight flagship universities discussed in the 2012 report are set out in the table below.

TABLE 1: Flagship universities selected by the project

UNIVERSITY	COUNTRY	SHORT FORM USED IN THIS MANUAL
University of Botswana	Botswana	Botswana
University of Cape Town	South Africa	UCT
University of Dar es Salaam	Tanzania	Dar es Salaam
Eduardo Mondlane University	Mozambique	Eduardo Mondlane
University of Ghana	Ghana	Ghana
Makerere University	Uganda	Makerere
University of Mauritius	Mauritius	Mauritius
University of Nairobi	Kenya	Nairobi

CHET accepted in the 2012 report that the third requirement for higher education performance measurements would have to be satisfied by any cross-national system: performance measurement must be based on quantitative data that are well-defined and understood across university systems in a range of different countries. The 2012 report acknowledges that satisfying this requirement was the most difficult aspect of CHET's first attempt at identifying sets of cross-national performance indicators.

CHET decided, in launching its first attempt, that data requirements for performance indicators could be met if the definitions and concepts built into the South African higher education management information system (HEMIS) were employed in the project. HEMIS includes definitions and concepts that can be found in higher education data systems in countries such as the USA, UK and Australia. Because CHET had access to Cape Town's HEMIS data, CHET sent, during 2007, data templates to the other seven universities listed in Table 1 above. The data templates were accompanied by notes defining the various concepts used and explaining how the calculations required should be made.

CHET found that many of the data tables returned during 2007 and early 2008 were inconsistent and incorrect. It decided that the best way of resolving these problems would be to send a task team to the universities concerned to discuss the templates, and to collect as much raw data as possible on site. The task team visited these seven universities during 2008.

In March 2009 CHET held a further workshop, which was attended by representatives of the seven universities based in countries other than South Africa. The data task team reported to the workshop that, by the beginning of 2009, all seven universities had been able to submit details of (a) formal qualifications offered, (b) head count student enrolments and graduates by qualification type and major fields of study, and (c) permanent academic, administrative and service staff. It reported further that only two of the seven universities had been able to provide information on full-time equivalent student enrolments, and that none had been able to provide full financial information in terms of the income and expenditure categories listed in the 2007 template.

The March 2009 workshop agreed that because the notions of (a) *full-time equivalent enrolled students within fields of study* and (b) *full-time equivalent academic staff members within fields of study* are central ones in higher education planning, all seven universities would attempt to provide these data. Those not able to extract the required information directly from their student and staff databases would use calculation guidelines provided by the CHET task team. By the end of 2009 most of the participating universities had been able to meet the commitments made at the March 2009 workshop. Work on filling gaps and eliminating inconsistencies continued into 2010.

1.3 Cross-national performance indicators: CHET's second project

CHET's second project on cross-national higher education data was launched at the end of 2011. The new project accepted, as the first project had, that information can serve different purposes, and that different information systems could be designed for securing different institutional goals and purposes. The new project also accepted that the management of information could serve as an important signal of a university's degree of coherence or fragmentation. These signals emerged clearly from the problems that had been encountered in the first collections of data from the selected flagship universities.

An additional South African university was added to the eight flagship universities listed in Table 1. This is Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (NMMU).

CHET decided that the major focuses of this second cross-national project should be on (a) resolving as many as possible of the problems encountered in the first project, (b) updating and extending the first project’s indicator databases, (c) developing new performance indicators and sharpening those appearing in each university’s academic core, and (d) developing further the information-processing capacity of the participating universities.

CHET decided further that to satisfy these four aspects, the outputs of the second project would have to be supported by the following:

- definitions and descriptions of the use of the data concepts needed for performance measurement and for cross-national comparisons; and
- examples of the use of the data for performance measurement within individual universities.

This document is intended to serve as a manual which satisfies these two components.

2 Data collection model and structure of manual

2.1 Data collection model

A major change has been made in the way in which data are being collected in this second cross-national project. The first project expected universities to extract data

from their student and staff databases, and then to complete sets of rigidly defined tables. This led to the various problems referred to earlier in this introduction. The diagram on page 4 sketches the main features of the different model that is applied in the second project.

The model requires universities to submit to CHET data which conforms to a prescribed framework. CHET checks and, if necessary, amends the incoming elements, and then uses them to generate various data tables. The CHET framework ensures (a) that these data tables are consistent across the different countries, and (b) that they are more extensive than those used in the first project. Cross-national performance indicators, as well as data essential for internal institutional performance measurement, can be extracted from these new data tables.

2.2 Structure of the manual

This document has been designed with these main purposes in mind:

1. It has to function as a 'user manual', in the sense of containing detailed explanations of terms and definitions, for institutional staff who are required (a) to extract the basic data required by the CHET framework, (b) to respond to any queries that may arise from the initial submissions of data, and (c) to interpret the data for the institution's planners and management.
2. It has to function as a 'user manual' in the further sense of giving institutional planners and analysts detailed explanations and examples of the kinds of data that can be extracted from the CHET framework.
3. It has also to provide more general, less specific, overviews of the uses of the CHET data framework, in particular of the uses of the data in institutional and in cross-national performance measurement.

STRUCTURE OF THE DATA MANUAL

To fulfil these different purposes, the first sections of the manual have been divided into two tracks. The technical track is intended to provide the ‘user manuals’ described in points (1) and (2) above, and the fast track the overviews outlined in point (3). The diagram on page 5 offers a summary of how the two tracks can be followed through this manual.

A reader who wants general overviews of the CHET data framework and of the uses of the data generated could skip the detail in Part Three and to move from Part Two directly to Parts Four, Five and Six. Others have two choices:

- They could use Part Two as a general introduction before moving to the technical track in Part Three. They would then move to the applications of the data in Parts Four, Five and Six.
- They could move directly from Part One to Part Three, and then to Parts Four, Five and Six.

PART TWO

SUMMARY OF CHET DATA FRAMEWORK

1 Programme and qualification mixes (PQMs)

The initial step in the CHET data framework involves universities listing by name or title all the degrees, diplomas and certificates they offer. These lists are organised, first by qualification type and then by fields of study, to produce programme and qualification mix (PQM) schedules for each university. Because standard definitions are used to produce the PQMs, these schedules become the basic data collection instruments in the CHET framework.

The data framework takes an ‘academic programme’ to be an ordered set of teaching/learning activities that eventually lead to the award of a *qualification* in one or more *fields of study*. Four simple qualification type categories are used in the framework: (1) undergraduate, (2) postgraduate below masters level, (3) masters, and (4) doctors. The fields of study categories are more complex.

The framework has retained the four basic fields of study categories used in the first cross-national performance indicator project. These are (a) science, engineering and technology (SET), (b) business, economics and management (BUS), (c) education (EDU), and (d) humanities and social sciences (HUM). It goes further than the first project by dividing the four categories into a number of sub-categories, to enable fuller accounts to be given of the range of subject matter offered by universities. This more detailed subject classification system is based on that used in South Africa’s higher education management and information system (HEMIS).

The HEMIS subject matter classification system has a hierarchical structure that consists of 20 first-order categories, and large numbers of second-order and third-order categories representing subfields of study. The CHET framework’s adaptation of the HEMIS system uses the 20 first-order categories, but only some of the second-order subcategories. The 20 first-order categories are summarised in Table 2 on page 8. Appendix 1 lists the first-order as well as the second-order categories employed in the CHET framework.

The processes involved in preparing the detailed PQM of each participating university have been complicated by the large numbers of academic programmes that they offer. The CHET data framework, as was indicated earlier, takes the key elements in an academic programme to be the qualification offered and the field of study linked to that programme. Table 3 on page 9 points to the scale of the work involved by summarising the totals of academic programmes that appear in the PQMs of the universities which are participating in the second phase of the cross-national indicator projects.

TABLE 2: List of all first-order subject matter classifications

FIRST-ORDER CODE	FIRST-ORDER CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION OF FIRST-ORDER CATEGORY
Set01	Agriculture, agricultural operations	Concerned with the production and management of crops and meat, the breeding of agricultural animals and plants, the development of soil and forests, and the processing of food
Set02	Architecture and the built environment	Focuses on various aspects of architecture-related fields, including the application of the principles of planning to the development of urban areas, the design of different types of spaces for leisure and living purposes
Set03	Computer and information sciences	Concerned with all facets of electronic computing, including computer systems, computer networks and computer software, as well as the classification, storage, processing and dissemination of information
Set04	Engineering	Concerned with the application of mathematical and scientific principles to the solution of practical problems
Set05	Health professions and clinical sciences	Prepares individuals for practice in the health care professions and also focuses on the study of related clinical sciences
Set06	Family ecology and consumer sciences	Focuses on family systems and consumer sciences, as well as on human nutrition, apparel and textiles
Set07	Life sciences	Focuses on the biological and the non-clinical biomedical sciences
Set08	Physical sciences	Focuses on inanimate objects, processes of matter and energy and associated phenomena
Set09	Mathematics and statistics	Concerned with logical symbolic language and its applications to the solution of functional problems, and with the making of sound inferences in the face of uncertainty
Set10	Military sciences	The scientific study of the socio-political and geo-spatial environment in which the defence system of the country operates; the organisational dynamics of the military as an institution
Bus01	Business, economics and management	Concerned with the theory and practice of planning, managing, marketing, with the systematic study of production and the allocation of financial and human resources, as well as with the preparation of individuals for administration and management in hospitality and tourism industries
Edu01	Education	A broad area of study concerned with the science and practice of educating the population
Hum01	Visual and performing arts	Focuses on the creation and interpretation of works of art and on performances that use auditory, kinaesthetic and visual phenomena to express ideas and emotions in various forms
Hum02	Communication, journalism	Focuses on how news and reports in various media are produced, used and interpreted within and across different contexts, as well as on the effective application of communication knowledge and skills
Hum03	Languages, linguistics and literature	Concerned with structures used in speech and writing and with various other aspects of the literatures of various languages
Hum04	Law	Concerned with identifying and elaborating the principles and procedures laid down by legislation, the common law and judicial precedent and enforced by institutions of government
Hum05	Philosophy, religion and theology	Concerned with (1) the critical analysis of and reflection on the ideas, theories, categories, concepts and methods for describing and evaluating human experience and reality, and (2) religion and different theologies
Hum06	Psychology	Focuses on the behaviour of individuals, independently or collectively, and the physical and environmental bases of mental, emotional and neurological development and processes
Hum07	Public management and services	Concerned with the formulation, implementation, administration, evaluation and management of public policies, programmes and services, including criminal justice and correctional services
Hum08	Social sciences	Concerned with the social sciences, social institutions and social behaviour as well as the interpretation of past events, issues and cultures

The totals in Table 3 are inflated because most universities offer specific fields of study in more than one qualification at the same level. For example, a university could offer the field of mathematics in Bachelor of Arts, Bachelor of Commerce, Bachelor of Science and Bachelor of Social Science degrees. Because an academic programme links a named degree to a field of study, these would be reflected in the PQM as four separate programmes. Eduardo Mondlane has the most elegant PQM because it links each field of study to a single named qualification.

TABLE 3: Total academic programmes listed in PQMs of participating universities

UNIVERSITY	COUNTRY	TOTAL ACADEMIC PROGRAMMES IN PQM
Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University	South Africa	450
University of Cape Town	South Africa	360
University of Nairobi	Kenya	340
University of Ghana	Ghana	310
Makerere University	Uganda	295
University of Mauritius	Mauritius	260
University of Botswana	Botswana	235
University of Dar es Salaam	Tanzania	140
Eduardo Mondlane University	Mozambique	115
TOTAL		2 505

Table 4 offers a number of examples of the kinds of programmes that are listed in the PQMs of the participating universities. The lists are truncated because use is made of only the 20 first-order fields of study categories.

TABLE 4: Examples of academic programmes listed in PQMs

	DEGREE TYPE	UNIVERSITY	FIRST-ORDER CATEGORY
SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY			
Certificate in Statistics	Undergraduate	Ghana	Set09 Mathematics & statistics
Diploma in Agriculture	Undergraduate	Mauritius	Set01 Agriculture, Agricultural Operations
Bachelor of Architecture	Undergraduate	Botswana	Set02 Architecture & the built environment
BSc in Botanical Sciences	Undergraduate	Dar es Salaam	Set07 Life sciences
Bachelor of Veterinary Medicine	Undergraduate	Nairobi	Set05 Health professions & related clinical sciences
Licenciatura in Medicine	Undergraduate	Eduardo Mondlane	Set05 Health professions & related clinical sciences
Postgraduate Diploma in IT	Postgraduate below masters	Makerere	Set03 Computer & information sciences
Postgraduate Diploma in Civil Engineering	Postgraduate below masters	Dar es Salaam	Set04 Engineering
Masters in Sustainable Aquaculture	Masters	Eduardo Mondlane	Set01 Agriculture, Agricultural Operations
MSc Textile Technology	Masters	Mauritius	Set06 Family ecology and consumer sciences
Doctor of Philosophy in Property Studies	Doctors	Cape Town	Set02 Architecture & the built environment
Doctor of Philosophy in Engineering	Doctors	Nairobi	Set04 Engineering
Master of Public Administration	Masters		Hum07 Public management & services
BUSINESS, MANAGEMENT			
Bachelor of Business Science	Undergraduate	Cape Town	Bus01 Business, economics & management sciences
Bachelor of Science in Administration	Undergraduate	Ghana	Bus01 Business, economics & management sciences
BSc (Hons) Human Resource Management	Undergraduate	Mauritius	Bus01 Business, economics & management sciences
EDUCATION			
Licenciatura in Portuguese Teaching	Undergraduate	Eduardo Mondlane	Edu01 Education
Master of Education	Masters	Dar es Salaam	Edu01 Education
HUMANITIES & SOCIAL SCIENCES			
Bachelor of Journalism & Communication	Undergraduate	Makerere	Hum05 Communication, journalism
Bachelor of Arts (Honours) in Sociology	Postgraduate below masters	Cape Town	Hum08 Social sciences
Master of Philosophy in Music	Masters	Ghana	Hum01 Visual & performing arts
Master of Public Administration	Masters	Botswana	Hum07 Public management & services

2 Student enrolment and graduate tables

The programme and qualification mix (PQM) schedules of each university serve as the templates used for the reporting and recording of their student enrolment and graduate information. Various definitions have to be employed when student and graduate data are recorded. The key ones that should be noted for the fast track are these:

- Head count student enrolment: A head count enrolment total treats all students, full-time or part-time, as one unit, without taking account of the course load carried by the student. So, a part-time student taking only one course would be counted as a unit, as would a full-time student who happens to be following only half of the normal curriculum in a given academic year. There are no fractions of students in a head count total.
- Full-time equivalent student enrolment: A full-time equivalent (FTE) student is a student who is taking, in a given academic year, all the prescribed courses in a standard full-time curriculum. A student taking the equivalent of 20% more than the standard curriculum would = 1.20 FTE students, and one taking only 60% standard full-time curriculum would = 0.60 students. An FTE student enrolment total is simply the sum of all the fractions calculated.
- Graduate totals: A graduate is a student who has satisfied all the requirements for the award of a qualification that appears on the institution's PQM. A graduate total takes all graduates as units, regardless of whether they were registered as full-time or part-time students.

Table 5 uses a selection of data of the University of Botswana as an example. It illustrates the link between a PQM and student enrolment and graduate data. Botswana's full PQM appears in Appendix 2 and its full set of enrolment and graduate data appears in Appendix 3. The academic programmes in Table 5 amount to less than 25% of the full lists of programmes. Table 5 is organised in the same way as the full table in Appendix 3:

- Column 2 lists qualifications under qualification type headings, from undergraduate certificate to doctoral degree.
- Column 3 organises the qualifications by first-order subject matter classification within broad fields in the order: (a) science and technology (b) business and management, (c) education (d) humanities and social sciences.
- Column 4 organises the qualifications by second-order subject matter classification, within each first-order category.
- The next three main columns give the enrolment and graduate data for each qualification, for three academic years: 2008/09, 2009/10, 2010/11. Data on part-time students are recorded, because Botswana was able to extract this information from its student record database.

Calculations of FTE student enrolments can be complex if, in accordance with the definition above, account is taken of the course loads of individual students. Simpler methods can, however, be employed. For example, full-time students could be assumed to be equivalent, on average, to 1 FTE student, and part-time students to 0.5 FTE students. If this method were applied to the sample of enrolment data in Table 5, the head count totals would be reduced by 5%. In the case of the 2010/11 the head count total of 7 583 would reduce to an FTE total of 7 210. It should be noted that FTE calculations do not apply to graduate totals.

TABLE 5: University of Botswana: extracts from detailed enrolment and graduate table

QUALIFICATION TITLE	QUALIFICATION TYPE	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	ENROLMENTS: FULL-TIME			ENROLMENTS: PART-TIME			GRADUATES		
				2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
Bachelor of Science (Urban & Regional Planning)	Undergraduate	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Sei0201: Urban & regional planning	43	42	47	0	0	0	12	8	14
Bachelor of Science (Information Technology)	Undergraduate	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Sei0301: Computer sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Science (Mechanical Engineering)	Masters	SET04: Engineering	Sei0410: Mechanical engineering	3	3	3	8	6	8	0	1	0
Bachelor of Engineering (Industrial Engineering)	Undergraduate	SET04: Engineering	Sei0419: Industrial Engineering	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
Certificate in Land Administration	Undergraduate	SET04: Engineering	Sei0420: Surveying engineering	0	0	23	0	0	0	0	0	23
Bachelor of Geomatics	Undergraduate	SET04: Engineering	Sei0420: Surveying engineering	3	38	67	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Medicine (Internal medicine)	Masters	SET05: Health sciences	Sei0506: Medicine	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Nursing Science (Generic)	Undergraduate	SET05: Health sciences	Sei0508: Nursing	200	202	226	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Chemistry)	Doctors	SET08: Physical sciences	Sei0803: Chemistry	5	5	7	0	0	0	0	0	3
Doctor of Philosophy (Natural Resource Management)	Doctors	SET08: Physical sciences	Sei0807: Environmental sciences	9	6	4	1	1	0	2	0	1
Master of Business Administration	Masters	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Busi0101: Business administration	22	29	26	139	133	121	35	51	42
Bachelor of Accountancy	Undergraduate	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Busi0102: Accounting	552	576	636	165	153	156	107	106	126
Bachelor of Finance	Undergraduate	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Busi0105: Banking & finance	189	212	228	67	84	94	47	47	41
Bachelor of Education (Secondary Education)	Undergraduate	EDU01: Education	EdU0102: Secondary education	248	227	294	0	0	0	62	80	40
Diploma in Adult Education	Undergraduate	EDU01: Education	EdU0103: Post-school education	26	22	24	34	24	17	22	24	14
Bachelor of Media Studies	Undergraduate	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication, media studies	115	110	129	0	0	0	27	21	24
Master of Public Administration (Public Policy & Administration)	Masters	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	2	4	3	1	0	0	1	3	3
Bachelor of Arts (Social Sciences)	Undergraduate	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0800: Second-order distinctions not made	1285	1366	1479	0	0	0	207	208	234
Diploma in Archives & Records Management	Undergraduate	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	47	30	43	0	0	0	31	16	11

3 Academic staffing

3.1 Basic points

Academics are a key input for the teaching and research activities of universities, and are therefore reported and analysed in detail in the CHET framework. A difference is drawn in these analyses between (a) permanent academic staff and (b) full-time equivalent (FTE) academic staff. The framework requires that all academic staff be linked to an academic unit in the university. The following points should be noted:

(1) *Academic staff member*: An academic staff member is defined as an employee who spends at least 50% of her/his official time on duty on teaching and/or research activities.

(2) *Permanent academic staff*: The framework permits the permanent/temporary distinction to be made in two ways: (a) A staff member can be classified as permanent if she/he contributes to an approved retirement fund of the university, and as temporary if she/he does not; or (b) a staff member can be classified as permanent if she/he holds a full-time contract of more than three years, and as temporary if she/he does not have such a contract.

(3) *Full-time equivalent academic staff*: FTE academic staff totals are used as measures of the staffing resources available to a university and to its various academic units.

(4) *Academic units*: Academic units are, for the reporting of permanent and FTE academic staff totals, taken to include academic departments, academic schools, research institutes, research centres, or any other grouping involved in teaching and/or research.

(5) *Academic staff properties*: The following features of individual academic staff members are aggregated into tables of permanent academic staff members:

- gender;
- highest formal qualification held during the reporting year: doctors or masters or below masters level; and
- academic rank held during the reporting year: full professor, associate professor, senior lecturer, lecturer, assistant lecturer; junior lecturer (or other appropriate titles).

The features listed above are not required for FTE academic staff analyses. Totals per academic unit are all that are required.

(6) *Major fields of study*: A major field of study for teaching and/or research activities has to be assigned to each academic unit for the reporting year. These fields must be selected from those used in the university's programme and qualification mix (PQM) analysis.

Table 6 is an extract from the academic staffing data submitted by Makerere University for the 2010/11 academic year. The table contains a selection of 4 of Makerere's 20 main academic units, and 30 of the 112 fields of study in which these units are active. The full academic staffing submission for Makerere for 2010/11 appears in Appendix 4.

TABLE 6: Extract from Makerere University's staff in data submission for 2010/11

NAME OF ACADEMIC UNIT	SUBJECT AREA	TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	PERMANENT ACADEMIC STAFF					BY HIGHEST QUALIFICATION			FTE ACADEMIC STAFF				
			BY RANK			BY GENDER		Doctoral degrees	Masters degrees	Below masters degrees		Not reported			
			Professors	Associate professors	Senior lecturers	Lecturers	Junior lecturers	Female	Male						
AGRICULTURE	Agricultural Economics & Agribusiness	16	0	4	0	8	4	6	10	8	8	0	0	14.3	
	Agricultural Engineering	12	0	0	2	3	7	2	10	1	9	2	0	10.9	
	Agricultural Extension/Education	12	0	1	1	6	4	5	7	6	6	0	0	11.9	
	Animal Science	12	1	1	3	3	4	3	9	4	8	0	0	11.2	
	Crop Science	18	2	2	7	4	3	5	13	11	7	0	0	18.8	
	Food Science and Technology	14	2	3	2	4	3	5	9	9	3	1	1	16.0	
	Soil Science	9	0	1	2	5	1	2	7	3	6	0	0	8.8	
	Subtotal for Agriculture	93	5	12	17	33	26	28	65	42	47	3	1	91.9	
	ARTS	Geography	21	1	2	1	7	10	3	18	7	12	2	0	17.2
		History	17	0	1	1	11	4	2	15	7	8	0	2	15.0
Languages		36	3	0	1	9	23	16	20	7	24	3	2	26.7	
Literature		14	0	4	3	4	3	4	10	6	7	0	1	14.1	
Mass Communication		10	0	2	0	2	6	4	6	1	6	3	0	7.9	
Music, Dance and Drama		12	0	2	3	3	4	3	9	6	4	2	0	13.5	
Philosophy		10	0	4	1	3	2	1	9	7	2	1	0	9.3	
Religious Studies		12	0	0	1	10	1	3	9	8	3	0	1	11.5	
Subtotal for Arts		132	4	15	11	49	53	36	96	49	66	11	6	115.2	
SCIENCE		Biochemistry	17	1	1	1	9	5	3	14	8	6	1	2	15.9
	Botany	13	2	3	2	3	3	5	8	4	4	1	0	14.9	
	Chemistry	20	2	1	3	8	6	2	18	4	12	1	3	18.2	
	Sport sciences	2	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	3.7	
	Geology	12	0	2	2	3	5	5	7	6	6	0	0	9.8	
	Mathematics	18	2	1	1	7	7	3	15	5	10	2	1	16.5	
	Physics	15	3	1	1	5	5	1	14	10	3	1	1	15.5	
	Zoology	18	1	4	4	5	4	5	13	12	5	0	1	19.9	
	Subtotal for Sciences	115	11	13	14	40	37	26	89	53	48	6	8	114.4	
	TECHNOLOGY	Architecture	14	0	2	1	6	5	5	9	6	1	1	1	14.1
Civil Engineering		20	2	0	4	5	9	2	18	3	14	1	2	18.4	
Construction Economics & Management		6	0	1	0	0	5	2	4	1	2	2	1	6.2	
Electrical Engineering		18	0	2	3	5	8	3	15	6	8	3	1	20.0	
Engineering Mathematics		3	0	0	1	1	2	0	3	1	2	0	0	2.3	
Mechanical Engineering		15	0	2	3	6	4	2	13	9	5	1	0	15.2	
Surveying		11	0	0	2	5	4	2	9	2	5	1	3	11.7	
Subtotal for Technology	87	2	7	13	28	37	16	71	28	42	9	8	87.9		

3.2 Linking academic staffing to programme and qualification mixes (PQMs)

Table 6 and Appendix 4 contain all the information on permanent academic staff listed above, and include, as a final column, the results of the FTE academic calculations for each field of study. What needs to be added now is a link between the staffing tables and the Makerere's PQM, to enable analyses to be made of the use of academic staffing resources in different academic programmes.

Table 7 offers this link by showing how Makerere's academic units and subject areas can be absorbed into the four broad fields of studies used at the start of analyses of PQMs. Table 15 in subsection 3.6 of the technical track gives a more detailed example, in which Makerere's permanent and FTE academic staff in 2010/11 are distributed between the 20 first-order categories in the data framework

TABLE 7: Allocation of Makerere University's academic staff to broad fields of study: 2010/11 only

BROAD FIELD OF STUDIES	PERMANENT ACADEMIC STAFF												FTE ACADEMIC STAFF TOTALS
	TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	BY RANK					BY GENDER		BY HIGHEST QUALIFICATION				
		Professors	Associate professors	Senior lecturers	Lecturers	Junior lecturers	Female	Male	Doctoral degrees	Masters degrees	Below masters degrees	Not reported	
Science & technology	743	49	74	106	249	265	197	546	231	391	77	44	730
Business & management	57	1	0	5	11	40	14	43	7	44	3	3	48
Education	101	1	2	14	42	42	32	69	35	54	10	2	89
Humanities & social sciences	308	17	27	46	105	113	104	204	101	156	20	31	277
TOTALS	1 209	68	103	171	407	460	347	862	374	645	110	80	1 144

4 Move to technical track

Part Three of the manual opens the technical track. It covers in detail material summarised in earlier sections of Part Two. The fast and technical tracks of the manual merge in Part Four.

PART THREE

TECHNICAL TRACK: DEVELOPING THE CHET DATA FRAMEWORK

1 Constructing programme and qualification mixes (PQMs)

1.1 Purpose of technical track

This detailed track is designed to assist those who are responsible for preparing the PQM of a university in accordance with the requirements of the CHET data framework. It contains definitions of terms, and guidelines for their application.

1.2 Qualifications

A qualification is the degree, diploma or certificate that a university awards to a student who satisfies all the requirements of an academic programme. The data framework does not distinguish between these three kinds of qualification, because national policies differ on their use. The data framework makes use only of the broad categories of undergraduate, postgraduate below masters level, masters, and doctors, which are defined in these ways:

- *Undergraduate*: These are normally entry-level qualifications which do not require prior university studies.
- *Postgraduate below masters*: These are normally qualifications that have an undergraduate qualification as an entry requirement. They are typically described as ‘postgraduate diplomas’ or ‘postgraduate certificates’.
- *Masters*: These are normally qualifications that use the term ‘masters’ in their titles, and that have either a bachelors degree or other postgraduate qualification as an entry requirement.
- *Doctors*: These are normally qualifications that use the term ‘doctor’ in their titles, and that have either a master’s degree or other postgraduate qualification as an entry requirement.

The use of the suffix ‘honours’ in degrees such as Bachelor of Arts (Honours) or Bachelor of Science (Honours) offers a good example of how potentially misleading degree titles can be. In Mauritius these two degrees are entry level qualifications and as a result are classified as ‘undergraduate’. In South Africa, honours degrees are fourth-year qualifications that follow on from the award of a three-year bachelor’s degree. They are therefore classified as ‘postgraduate below masters’.

1.3 Fields of study

Fields of study are defined as the major or principal subjects followed by students in their qualifications. These major subjects can sometimes be read off the title of a qualification, but often cannot be. Examples of cases where the title is linked to a field of studies can be seen in Table 4 in Section 1 of Part Two. There are, however, many examples of general qualifications such as Bachelor of Arts, Bachelor of Commerce, and Bachelor of Science where the fields of study cannot be read off the title, and where detailed institutional knowledge and analyses are needed.

To make the data comparable across different universities, when a field of study has been identified it must be placed into a standard classification that applies to all the universities involved. CHET has decided to use an adapted version of the South African subject matter classification system in its data framework. The CHET framework does, however, retain the four basic fields of study categories that were used in the first cross-national performance indicator project. These are (a) science, engineering and technology (SET), (b) business, economics and management (BUS), (c) education (EDU), and (d) humanities and social sciences (HUM).

South Africa has, for the past 30 years, employed a subject matter classification system in the reporting and analysis of national higher education data. The first version of the classification system report was based on a 1977 report published by the National Centre for Education Statistics in the USA. A revised version of the South African classification system was developed during 2007 and published in August 2008. This can be seen, under the title *Classification of Education Subject Matter*, on the website of the South African Department of Higher Education and Training (www.dhet.gov.za).

The 2008 South African report stresses that the subject matter classification system is not intended for use as a framework for the organisation of institutions, faculties, departments and other educational groupings. The main focus of the classification system is on the knowledge components that academic programmes are designed to deliver. The South African subject matter classification system has a hierarchical structure that consists of 20 first-order categories, each of which is divided into second-order categories which define key sub-fields. The second-order categories are divided in turn into third-order categories, which define sub-sub-fields.

CHET's adaptation of the South African subject matter classification system uses the 20 first-order categories but clusters these into the four broad subject matter groups that were used in the first round of data collection. Although use is made of all 20 of the South African first-order classification categories, CHET has decided (a) not to use the third-order categories, and (b) to employ a limited set of second-order categories. The number of fields of study categories used in the CHET framework is still extensive. As can be seen in Table 8 below, a total of 20 first-order and 171 second-order subject matter categories are included in the framework.

TABLE 8: Total first and second-order subject matter categories by broad fields of study

BASIC SUBJECT DIVISIONS	TOTAL FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT CATEGORIES	TOTAL SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT CATEGORIES
Science & technology	10	100
Business, management	1	13
Education	1	11
Humanities & social science	8	47
Totals	20	171

1.4 Examples of applications of qualification and fields of study categories

Tables 9 and 10, which follow on the next page, contain short extracts from the PQMs of the University of Botswana and the University of Ghana. Table 9 lists only 25 of Ghana's 310 academic programmes, and 20 of Botswana's 235 academic programmes. Some general points to note about the two tables are these:

- Column A contains the names or titles of the qualification used by the university in its record systems. The general practice adopted by universities has been to list only 'live' qualifications, i.e. those for which students are able to register in the reporting year. All live qualifications are listed even if they appear to be duplicates, such as these:
 - Master of Science in Physics
 - Master of Philosophy in Physics
 - Bachelor of Arts in Economics
 - Bachelor of Science in Economics
 - Bachelor of Commerce in Economics
- Column B places all the qualifications listed into one of the four qualification categories. This is a straightforward process, and will depend on both the title of the qualification and the regulations of the university.
- Column C links each qualification to one of the four broad fields of study used in the first cross-national performance indicator project.
- Column D divides the broad field of study of each qualification into one of the 20 first-order categories, which are listed and defined in Table 2 of Part Two. This is a straightforward process, with note having to be taken of only one specific issue. This is that on occasions, specific fields of study often cannot be allocated to general degrees in science and technology and in humanities. An example can be seen in row 1 of Table 10. This shows that Ghana offers a Bachelor of Science (General) degree to which no specific field of study is attached. This has had to be coded as SET00 in Column D.
- Column E uses Appendix 1 to link the first-order fields of study of qualifications to an appropriate second-order category. This relies heavily on those involved in the process (a) knowing the academic structure of their degrees, and (b) understanding the details of the CHET data framework. Some specific issues should be noted when the second-order classifications are used:
 - A qualification should be linked to only one specific second-order category. If this is not possible, for example in a general degree or a degree that is linked to more than one field of study, then use should be made of the '00' suffix. The Bachelor of Arts (Social Sciences) degree that appears on the second last row of Table 9 is an example. The first-order category for this qualification is clearly HUM08: social sciences. It has, however, to be given a final coding of HUM0800 because no specific major field is identified.
 - Use should be made of the second-order category 'other' in cases in which a specific field of study is known, but for which no appropriate second-order category appears in Appendix 1.

Appendix 2 sets out as an example the full PQM of the University of Botswana. This shows how its qualifications have had to be ordered by qualification type, and first- and second-order fields of study. As will be seen in the next two sections, the CHET data framework uses these PQMs as templates for the recording of data on student enrolments and graduates.

TABLE 9: University of Botswana: Extracts from programme and qualification mix

COLUMN A INSTITUTIONAL QUALIFICATION TITLE	COLUMN B QUALIFICATION TYPE	COLUMN C BROAD FIELDS OF STUDY	COLUMN D FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	COLUMN E SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION
Bachelor of Science (Urban & Regional Planning)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0201: Urban & regional planning
Bachelor of Science (Information Technology)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences
Master of Science (Mechanical Engineering)	Masters	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0410: Mechanical engineering
Bachelor of Engineering (Industrial Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0419: Industrial Engineering
Certificate in Land Administration	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering
Bachelor of Geomatics	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering
Master of Medicine (Internal medicine)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Bachelor of Nursing Science (Generic)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing
Doctor of Philosophy (Chemistry)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry
Doctor of Philosophy (Natural Resource Management)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Master of Business Administration	Masters	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration
Bachelor of Accountancy	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0102: Accounting
Bachelor of Finance	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0105: Banking & finance
Bachelor of Education (Secondary Education)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Diploma in Adult Education	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0103: Post-school education
Bachelor of Media Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication, media studies
Master of Public Administration (Public Policy & Administration)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration
Bachelor of Arts (Social Sciences)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0800: 2nd-order distinctions not made
Diploma in Archives & Records Management	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science

TABLE 10: University of Ghana: Extracts from programme and qualification mix

COLUMN A INSTITUTIONAL QUALIFICATION TITLE	COLUMN B QUALIFICATION TYPE	COLUMN C BROAD FIELDS OF STUDY	COLUMN D FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	COLUMN E SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION
Bachelor of Science (General)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET00: Science general	SET000: No 1st- or 2nd-order distinctions made
Master of Philosophy in Agricultural Administration	Masters	Science & technology	SET01: Agriculture	Set0101: Agriculture business, economics
Diploma in Agriculture (Animal production & Health)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET01: Agriculture	Set0102: Agriculture science & production
Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (Horticulture)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET01: Agriculture	Set0103: Applied horticulture
Bachelor of Arts in Information Studies	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences
Bachelor of Science in Engineering (Biomedical Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0403: Biomedical engineering
Master of Science in Petroleum Geoscience	Masters	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0416: Petroleum Engineering
Bachelor of Dental Surgery	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0503: Dentistry & oral sciences
Bachelor of Science in Physiotherapy	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0515: Rehab & Therapeutic
Doctor of Philosophy in Insect Science	Doctors	Science & technology	SET07: Life sciences	Set0706: Zoology, entomology
Master of Philosophy in Nuclear & Radiochemistry	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry
Bachelor of Arts in Geography & Resource Development	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0804: Geography
Diploma in Accounting	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0102: Accounting
Bachelor of Science in Administration (Accounting)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0102: Accounting
Master of Philosophy in Economics	Masters	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics
Doctor of Philosophy in Adult Education	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0103: Post-school education
Diploma in Adult Education	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104: Post-school education
Bachelor of Arts in Dance Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM01: Visual & performing arts	Hum0101: Dance
Bachelor of Music	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM01: Visual & performing arts	Hum0106: Music
Master of Arts in Communication Studies	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication studies
Master of Philosophy in Study of Religion	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM05: Philosophy & religion	Hum0502: Religion
Doctor of Philosophy in Archaeology	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0802: Archaeology
Master of Philosophy in Information Studies	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library sciences
Bachelor of Arts in Social Work	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work

2 Student enrolments and graduates

2.1 Standard definitions

The main definitions are employed in the compiling of student data tables are these:

2.1.1 Student

A higher education student is someone who meets the following two conditions:

- he/she satisfies the institution's minimum requirements for entry into undergraduate level studies; and
- he/she is enrolled for a qualification that is included in the PQM of the university.

2.1.2 Occasional student

This is a person who (a) satisfies the minimum requirements for entry into the institution, (b) is registered for a course that is included in the curriculum of at least one qualification included in the PQM of the university, but (c) who is not registered for any qualification.

2.1.3 Full-time and part-time students

No standard definitions can be given of these categories. A full-time student is someone regarded by the institution as full-time, and a part-time student is someone regarded by the institution as part-time. The distinction is often based on the institution's expectation of the fees a student is expected to pay.

2.1.4 Full-time equivalent students

A full-time equivalent (FTE) student is a student who is taking, in a given academic year, all the prescribed courses in a standard full-time curriculum. A student taking 20% more than the standard curriculum would = 1.20 FTE students, and one taking only 60% of a standard full-time curriculum would = 0.60 students.

2.1.5 Head count student enrolment

A head count enrolment total treats all students, full-time or part-time, as one unit, without taking account of the course load carried by the student. So an occasional student taking only one course would be counted as a unit, as would a student who is registered for a degree but is following only half of the normal curriculum for an academic year.

2.1.6 Full-time equivalent student enrolment

An FTE student enrolment total is simply the sum of all the fractions calculated.

2.1.7 Graduates

A graduate is a student who has satisfied all the requirements for the award of a qualification that appears on the institution's PQM.

2.1.8 Graduate totals

A graduate total takes all graduates as units, regardless of whether they had been registered as full-time or part-time students.

2.2 Linking enrolment and graduate totals to PQMs

Enrolment and graduate totals are, in the CHET framework, linked directly to a university's PQM. The PQM serves as a data template, in the sense that each row must reflect an enrolment and graduate total, even if these are zero. Table 8 in on page 17 uses a selection of data of the University of Botswana as examples of how PQM and enrolment data are to be linked. Botswana's full PQM appears in Appendix 2 and its full set of enrolment and graduate data appear in Appendix 3.

2.3 FTE student enrolment calculations

Fulfilling the requirements of the definition of an FTE student could lead to complex calculations having to be made on the academic records of individual students. Because of this, universities were advised in the previous phase of data collection to apply any simpler methods that could best suit their circumstances. This could include assuming that most full-time students follow all the courses required in a standard curriculum, and that most part-time students carry 50% of a full-time load. On these assumptions a full-time student would be equivalent to 1 FTE student, and a part-time student to 0.5 FTE students.

Table 11 on page 22 shows what the effect would be of applying this method to the sample of enrolment data in Table 8. The outcome would be that the FTE enrolment totals would be 5% lower than the corresponding head count totals.

3 Staffing categories

3.1 Standard definitions

3.1.1 *Staff member*

A staff member is a person who has been on the payroll of the university at some time during a specified year. Staff members include persons who:

- have full-time contracts;
- have part-time contracts;
- were on sick leave, long leave, sabbatical leave, maternity leave, study leave; and
- were on secondment to an external organisation, with the secondment being funded by the university.

Persons working for external organisations who are being paid by the university to provide 'outsourced' or hired services (e.g. for cleaning, grounds maintenance, building and plant maintenance, catering, security) are not to be counted as staff members. Their costs will be reported in the university's financial accounts as operating, rather than payroll, costs.

3.1.2 *Full-time and part-time staff*

The full-time/part-time status of a staff member is determined by her/his contract of employment with the university.

TABLE 11: University of Botswana: Extracts from detailed head count and FTE enrolments

QUALIFICATION TITLE	First-order SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	Second-order SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	TOTAL HEAD COUNT ENROLMENTS			ESTIMATED FULL-TIME EQUIVALENT ENROLLMENT			RATIOS OF FTE TO HEAD COUNT STUDENTS		
			2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
Certificate in Archives & Records Management	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	13	13	2	13	13	2	100%	100%	100%
Diploma in Mining Engineering	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and Mineral Engineering	74	78	97	74	78	97	100%	100%	100%
Diploma in Statistics	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	75	72	79	75	72	79	100%	100%	100%
Diploma in Adult Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104: Post-school education	60	46	41	43	34	33	72%	74%	79%
Diploma in Non-Governmental Organization Management	EDU01: Education	Bus0113: Business, economics other	12	11	11	6	6	6	50%	50%	50%
Diploma in Law	HUM04: Law	Hum0400: 2nd-order distinctions not made	117	109	53	117	109	53	100%	100%	100%
Diploma in Social Work	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work	79	79	87	79	79	87	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Science (General)	SET00: General	SET000: No 1st- or 2nd-order distinctions made	1337	1209	1129	1337	1209	1129	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Science (Urban & Regional Planning)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0201: Urban & regional planning	43	42	47	43	42	47	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Science (Computer Science)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences	76	61	107	76	61	107	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Engineering (Civil Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0405: Civil engineering	110	115	103	110	115	103	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Science (Mining Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and Mineral Engineering	42	41	28	42	41	28	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Medicine Bachelor of Surgery	SET05: Health sciences	Set0507: Medical clinical sciences	0	36	83	0	36	83		100%	100%
Bachelor of Nursing Science (Generic)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing	200	202	226	200	202	226	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Science (Environmental Health)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0513: Public Health	56	68	85	56	68	85	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Science (Geology)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0805: Geology	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Bachelor of Science (Applied Geophysics)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Bachelor of Science (Radiation and Health Physics)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Bachelor of Science (Environmental Science)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Bachelor of Science (Statistics)	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	3	1	2	3	1	1	100%	100%	50%
Bachelor of Business Administration (Management)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	515	518	597	419	426	498	81%	82%	83%
Bachelor of Accountancy	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0102: Accounting	717	729	792	635	653	714	88%	90%	90%
Bachelor of Education (Primary Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0101: Primary education	214	194	161	214	194	161	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Education (Secondary Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	73	76	99	73	76	99	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Education (Science Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	352	295	322	352	295	322	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Media Studies	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication, media studies	115	110	129	115	110	129	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Arts (Humanities)	HUM00	HUM000: No 1st- or 2nd-order distinctions made	1944	2089	2205	1944	2089	2205	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Psychology	HUM06: Psychology	Hum0608: Psychology other	13	14	15	13	14	15	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Arts (Library & Information Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	18	38	36	18	38	36	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Library & Information Studies	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	101	85	119	101	85	119	100%	100%	100%
Bachelor of Social Work	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work	291	286	303	291	286	303	100%	100%	100%
Postgraduate Diploma in Statistics	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	3	1	2	3	1	1	83%	100%	50%
Postgraduate Diploma in Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	236	137	81	236	137	81	100%	100%	100%
Master in Project Management	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0202: Construction, building	78	57	48	42	30	25	54%	53%	52%
Master of Science (Computer Science)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences	8	16	16	7	13	15	81%	81%	91%
Master of Science (Electrical & Electronic Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0407: Electrical engineering	23	24	17	19	17	13	83%	71%	74%
Master of Philosophy (Applied Microbiology)	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology	10	0	0	9	0	0	85%		
Master of Science (Chemistry)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry	12	12	12	12	12	12	100%	100%	100%
Master of Science (Environmental Science)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	27	27	21	23	22	19	83%	80%	88%
Master of Business Administration	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	161	162	147	92	96	87	57%	59%	59%
Master of Arts (Economics)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics	20	21	31	20	21	31	100%	100%	100%
Master in Education (Primary Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0101: Primary education	9	10	6	7	7	4	72%	70%	58%
Master of Education (Mathematics & Science)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	30	29	18	20	22	13	67%	76%	72%
Master of Philosophy (Geography Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Master of Education (Adult Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0104: Post-school education	26	25	24	17	19	15	65%	74%	63%
Master of Philosophy (Gender Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0			
Master of Arts (African Language & Literature)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	16	17	13	10	12	9	63%	71%	65%
Master of Philosophy (African Languages & Literature)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	0	1	1	0	1	1		100%	100%
Master of Arts (English)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	25	24	17	21	20	14	82%	81%	79%
Master of Philosophy (English)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	2	3	0	2	3	0	100%	83%	
Master of Public Administration (Human Resource Management)	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	45	60	63	31	38	39	69%	63%	61%
Master of Arts (Library & Information Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	30	30	22	20	21	15	67%	68%	66%
Master of Arts (Development Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	45	39	37	33	30	26	72%	77%	69%
Master of Arts (Population Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	24	33	34	20	25	25	83%	76%	72%
Doctor of Philosophy (Applied Microbiology)	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology	3	0	0	3	0	0	83%		
Doctor of Philosophy (Chemistry)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry	5	5	7	5	5	7	100%	100%	100%
Doctor of Philosophy (Environmental Science)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	10	7	4	10	7	4	95%	93%	100%
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Curriculum & Instruction)	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education	1	2	1	1	2	1	100%	100%	50%
Doctor of Philosophy (Library & Information Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	4	3	3	3	3	3	75%	83%	83%
TOTALS			7 503	7 362	7 583	7 110	6 991	7 219	95%	95%	95%

3.1.3 *Permanent and temporary staff*

The permanent/temporary distinction can be made in either of the following two ways:

- A staff member can be classified as permanent if she/he contributes to an approved retirement fund of the university, and as temporary if she/he does not.
- A staff member can be classified as permanent if she/he holds a full-time contract of more than three years, and as temporary if she/he does not have such a contract.

3.1.4 *Academic staff member*

An academic staff member is an employee who spends at least 50% of her/his official time on duty (i) on research activities and/or (ii) on instruction activities such as lecturing, conducting tutorials or practical sessions, marking assignments or examinations and preparing new curricula.

3.1.5 *Service staff member*

A service staff member is an employee whose duties involve unskilled activities such as cleaning of buildings, gardening, preparing food and serving food.

3.1.6 *Administrative staff member*

An administrative staff member is a non-academic staff member who functions at levels above that of service staff. This category will include the executive management of the university, deans of faculties (if they spend less than 50% of the official time on teaching and/or research), heads of administrative sections, and other administrative staff such as technicians, librarians, computer staff, accountants and office staff.

3.1.7 *Full-time equivalent employee*

A full-time equivalent (FTE) employee is a staff member who works at the university on a *full-time* basis for the 12 months of the reporting year.

3.2 Calculating full-time equivalent (FTE) staff values

3.2.1 *FTE values of full-time staff*

An employee who is classified as 'full-time' and who appears on the payroll of the university for 12 months must always = 1.0 FTE employees. The FTE value of a full-time staff member will be less than 1.0 in the following circumstances:

- The staff member had a full-time employment contract for less than the full reporting year (e.g. she/he commenced work after the start of the year or left before the end of the reporting year).
- The staff member took unpaid leave for part of the reporting year.
- The staff member was absent for part of the reporting year on a secondment to an external organisation that was funded by the external organisation.

The following types of absences do not reduce the FTE value for a staff member: sick leave, long leave, sabbatical leave, maternity leave, study leave, and secondments that are funded by the university. Irrespective of the length of such absences, the FTE value for a staff member who is employed for a full year on a full-time basis must be equal to 1.0.

3.2.2 FTE values of part-time staff

A staff member who is classified as 'part-time' must always = less than 1.0 FTE employees. The fraction of an FTE unit assigned to a part-time staff member can be determined in two ways:

- The employment contract can be used if this indicates what proportion of a full-time load the staff member will be carrying. For example, if the contract specifies that the staff member has a 50% load for 12 months, then she/he will be equivalent to 0.5 FTE employees. If the contract gives the staff member a 33% load for nine months, then she/he will = $0.33 \times 9/12 = 0.25$ FTE employees.
- If the only information available is the amount paid to a staff member over the year, then her/his FTE value can be determined as: total amount paid divided by the standard cost-of-employment of an employee in that staff category. For example, if the average cost to the university of a full-time staff member in the category is (say) 100 000 (currency units), and if the part-time employee was paid a total of 10 000 during the reporting year, then her/his FTE value will be $10\ 000/100\ 000 = 0.1$ FTE employees.

3.3 Academic staffing

An academic staff member was defined in 3.1.4 above as an employee who spends at least 50% of her/his official time on duty (i) on research activities and/or (ii) on instruction activities. Academics are a key input for the teaching and research activities of universities; they are, as a consequence, the main staffing resource reported and analysed in the CHET framework. A difference is drawn in these analyses between (a) permanent academic staff and (b) full-time equivalent (FTE) academic staff.

3.3.1 Permanent academic staff

The following features of individual staff members are aggregated in tables of permanent academic staff members:

- gender;
- highest formal qualification held during the reporting year: doctors or masters or below masters level; and
- academic rank held during the reporting year: full professor, associate professor, senior lecturer, lecturer, assistant professor; junior lecturer (or other appropriate titles).

3.3.2 Full-time equivalent academic staff

FTE academic staff totals are used as measures of the staffing resources available to a university and to its various academic units. The features listed in 3.3.1 are not required for FTE academic staff analyses. Totals per academic unit are all that are required.

3.3.3 Academic units

Academic units are, for the reporting of permanent and FTE academic staff totals, taken to include academic departments, academic schools, research institutes, research centres, or any other grouping involved in teaching and/or research.

A major field of studies for teaching and/or research activities has to be assigned to each academic unit for the reporting year. These fields must be selected from those used in the university's programme and qualification mix (PQM) analysis.

3.4 Academic staffing calculations

A brief example can now be offered of the applications of the various definitions above to an academic unit. Suppose that a Department of Animal Production had the following academic staff complement in 2010/11:

- Full-time academics on contracts longer than three years:
 - 2 professors employed for 12 months in the reporting year
 - 4 senior lecturers (3 employed for 12 months, 1 employed for 8 months)
 - 6 lecturers (4 employed for 12 months, 1 employed for 6 months, 1 for 3 months)
 - 2 research officers (employed at lecturer level for 12 months)
 - Total = 14 (9 with doctorates & 5 with masters; 4 females & 10 males)
- Part-time academics:
 - 1 associate professor on a 40% contract for 6 months
 - 1 lecturer on a 50% contract for 12 months
 - 2 lecturers on a 60% contracts for 8 months
- Other payroll expenditure on part-time academics
 - Expenditure on laboratory demonstrators and tutors = 800 000 (currency units), while average cost to university of full-time lecturer = 180 000

The permanent academic staff complement would, for purposes of the CHET data framework, be analysed in this way:

TABLE 12: Example of permanent academic reporting

DEPARTMENT OF ANIMAL PRODUCTION IN 2010/11: PERMANENT ACADEMICS	
Field of studies: SET0102: Agricultural science & production	
Permanent academics by rank	
Professors	2
Senior lecturers	4
Lecturers (including research officers)	8
Total	14
Permanent academics by gender	
Female	4
Male	10
Permanent academics by highest formal qualification	
Doctors degree	9
Masters degree	5
Below masters	0
Total	14

The full-time equivalent academic staffing resources would be calculated as illustrated in Table 13.

TABLE 13: Example of FTE academic reporting

FULL-TIME EQUIVALENT ACADEMIC STAFF IN DEPARTMENT OF ANIMAL PRODUCTION		
	Calculation of FTE academic staff value	FTE total
2 permanent professors	2 full-time for 12 months = 2 FTE staff	2.0
4 permanent senior lecturers	3 full-time for 12 months = 3 FTE staff 1 full-time for 8 months = 0.67 FTE staff	3.67
6 permanent lecturers	4 full-time for 12 months = 4 FTE staff 1 full-time for 6 months = 0.50 FTE staff 1 full-time for 3 months = 0.25 FTE staff	4.75
2 permanent research officers	2 full-time for 12 months = 2 FTE staff	2.0
FTE total for permanent academics		12.42
1 part-time associate professor (part-time for 6 months on 40% contract)	$1 \times 6/12 \times 40\% = 0.20$ FTE staff	0.20
1 part-time lecturer (part-time for 12 months on 50% contract)	$1 \times 12/12 \times 50\% = 0.50$ FTE staff	0.50
2 part-time lecturers (part-time for 8 months on 60% contracts)	$2 \times 8/12 \times 60\% = 0.80$ FTE staff	0.80
Laboratory demonstrators and tutors	$800\ 000/180\ 000 = 4.44$ FTE staff	4.44
FTE total for part-time academics		5.94
FTE academic staff total for 2010 for Department of Animal Production		18.36

3.5 Extract from staffing data submitted by a university

Table 14 is an extract from the academic staffing data submitted by Makerere University for the 2010/11 academic year. The table contains a selection of 4 of Makerere's 20 main academic units, and 30 of the 112 fields of study in which these units are active. The full academic staffing submission for Makerere for 2010/11 appears in Appendix 4.

3.6 Linking academic staffing to programme and qualification mixes (PQMs)

Table 14 and Appendix 4 contain all the information on permanent academic staff listed in sub-section 3.3.1, and include, as a final column, the results of the FTE academic calculations for each field of study. What needs to be added now is a link between the staffing tables and the Makerere's PQM, to enable analyses to be made of the use of academic staffing resources in different academic programmes.

Table 15 offers this link by showing how Makerere's academic units and subject areas can be absorbed into the 20 first-order field of studies used in the analyses of PQMs and student enrolments and graduates.

TABLE 14: Extract from Makerere University's staff in data submission for 2010/11

NAME OF ACADEMIC UNIT	SUBJECT AREA	PERMANENT ACADEMIC STAFF												FTE ACADEMIC STAFF	
		TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	BY RANK					BY GENDER		BY HIGHEST QUALIFICATION					TOTALS
			Professors	Associate professors	Senior lecturers	Lecturers	Junior lecturers	Female	Male	Doctoral degrees	Masters degrees	Below masters degrees	Not reported		
AGRICULTURE	Agricultural Economics & Agribusiness	16	0	4	0	8	4	6	10	8	8	0	0	14.3	
	Agricultural Engineering	12	0	0	2	3	7	2	10	1	9	2	0	10.9	
	Agricultural Extension/Education	12	0	1	1	6	4	5	7	6	6	0	0	11.9	
	Animal Science	12	1	1	3	3	4	3	9	4	8	0	0	11.2	
	Crop Science	18	2	2	7	4	3	5	13	11	7	0	0	18.8	
	Food Science and Technology	14	2	3	2	4	3	5	9	9	3	1	1	16.0	
	Soil Science	9	0	1	2	5	1	2	7	3	6	0	0	8.8	
Subtotal for Agriculture		93	5	12	17	33	26	28	65	42	47	3	1	91.9	
ARTS	Geography	21	1	2	1	7	10	3	18	7	12	2	0	17.2	
	History	17	0	1	1	11	4	2	15	7	8	0	2	15.0	
	Languages	36	3	0	1	9	23	16	20	7	24	3	2	26.7	
	Literature	14	0	4	3	4	3	4	10	6	7	0	1	14.1	
	Mass Communication	10	0	2	0	2	6	4	6	1	6	3	0	7.9	
	Music, Dance and Drama	12	0	2	3	3	4	3	9	6	4	2	0	13.5	
	Philosophy	10	0	4	1	3	2	1	9	7	2	1	0	9.3	
	Religious Studies	12	0	0	1	10	1	3	9	8	3	0	1	11.5	
Subtotal for Arts		132	4	15	11	49	53	36	96	49	66	11	6	115.2	
SCIENCE	Biochemistry	17	1	1	1	9	5	3	14	8	6	1	2	15.9	
	Botany	13	2	3	2	3	3	5	8	8	4	1	0	14.9	
	Chemistry	20	2	1	3	8	6	2	18	4	12	1	3	18.2	
	Sport sciences	2	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	3.7	
	Geology	12	0	2	2	3	5	5	7	6	6	0	0	9.8	
	Mathematics	18	2	1	1	7	7	3	15	5	10	2	1	16.5	
	Physics	15	3	1	1	5	5	1	14	10	3	1	1	15.5	
	Zoology	18	1	4	4	5	4	5	13	12	5	0	1	19.9	
Subtotal for Sciences		115	11	13	14	40	37	26	89	53	48	6	8	114.4	
TECHNOLOGY	Architecture	14	0	2	1	6	5	5	9	6	6	1	1	14.1	
	Civil Engineering	20	2	0	4	5	9	2	18	3	14	1	2	18.4	
	Construction Economics & Management	6	0	1	0	0	5	2	4	1	2	2	1	6.2	
	Electrical Engineering	18	0	2	3	5	8	3	15	6	8	3	1	20.0	
	Engineering Mathematics	3	0	0	0	1	2	0	3	1	2	0	0	2.3	
	Mechanical Engineering	15	0	2	3	6	4	2	13	9	5	1	0	15.2	
	Surveying	11	0	0	2	5	4	2	9	2	5	1	3	11.7	
Subtotal for Technology		87	2	7	13	28	37	16	71	28	42	9	8	87.9	

TABLE 15: Allocation of Makerere University's academic staff to first-order fields of study: 2010/11

FIRST-ORDER FIELD OF STUDIES	PERMANENT ACADEMIC STAFF												FTE ACADEMIC STAFF TOTALS
	TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	BY RANK					BY GENDER		BY HIGHEST QUALIFICATION				
		Professors	Associate professors	Senior lecturers	Lecturers	Junior lecturers	Female	Male	Doctoral degrees	Masters degrees	Below masters degrees	Not reported	
SET01: AGRICULTURE, AGRICULTURAL OPERATIONS	130	8	17	22	42	41	36	94	55	65	8	2	129
SET02: ARCHITECTURE & BUILT ENVIRONMENT	14	0	2	1	6	5	5	9	6	6	1	1	14
SET03: COMPUTER & INFORMATION SCIENCE	48	0	1	6	3	38	18	30	7	32	7	2	38
SET04: ENGINEERING	73	2	5	12	22	32	11	62	22	36	8	7	74
SET05: HEALTH & CLINICAL SCIENCES	296	24	32	42	119	79	88	208	64	173	37	22	302
SET06: CONSUMER SCIENCES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
SET07: LIFE SCIENCES	50	4	8	7	17	14	15	35	28	17	2	3	54
SET08: PHYSICAL SCIENCES	81	8	7	10	24	32	12	69	34	36	7	4	71
SET09: MATHEMATICS & STATISTICS	51	3	2	6	16	24	12	39	15	26	7	3	48
SET08: MILITARY SCIENCES	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0
SUBTOTAL: SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY	743	49	74	106	249	265	197	546	231	391	77	44	730
SUBTOTAL: BUSINESS, ECONOMICS, MANAGEMENT	57	1	0	5	11	40	14	43	7	44	3	3	48
SUBTOTAL: EDUCATION	101	1	2	14	42	42	32	69	35	54	10	2	89
HUM01: VISUAL & PERFORMING ARTS	47	1	4	9	16	17	17	30	12	28	3	4	44
HUM02: COMMUNICATION & JOURNALISM	10	0	2	0	2	6	4	6	1	6	3	0	8
HUM03: LANGUAGES & LITERATURE	50	3	4	4	13	26	20	30	13	31	3	3	41
HUM04: LAW	44	3	5	2	9	25	17	27	3	29	2	10	34
HUM05: PHILOSOPHY, RELIGION	22	0	4	2	13	3	4	18	15	5	1	1	21
HUM06: PSYCHOLOGY	24	1	1	3	8	11	10	14	8	11	2	3	22
HUM07: PUBLIC MANAGEMENT & SERVICES	18	2	3	7	5	1	1	17	9	4	1	4	18
HUM08: SOCIAL SCIENCES	93	7	4	19	39	24	31	62	40	42	5	6	90
SUBTOTAL: HUMANITIES & SOCIAL SCIENCES	308	17	27	46	105	113	104	204	101	156	20	31	277
OVERALL TOTAL	1 209	68	103	171	407	460	347	862	374	645	110	80	1 143

PART FOUR

EXTRACTING DATA TABLES

1 Purpose of Part Four

Subsection 1.3 of the Introduction sets out the main purposes of this manual as (a) resolving as many as possible of the problems encountered in the first cross-national project, (b) updating and extending the first project's indicator databases, (c) developing new performance indicators, and (d) developing, where necessary, the information-processing capacity of the participating universities. The Introduction added that to satisfy these four purposes, the manual would have to include definitions of the data concepts needed for performance measurement, and examples of the extracting of comparative tables from the data submitted by universities.

Part Four offers these examples through the construction of cross-national tables that cover the enrolment, graduate and academic staffing data of the nine participating universities.

A preliminary point to note about the tables that follow is that the dates of the academic years for the two South African universities differ from those of the other seven universities. An academic year in South Africa is a calendar year, so the dates for Cape Town and Nelson Mandela are shown as 2009, 2010 and 2011. The academic year for the other cross two calendar years, and are therefore shown as 2008/09, 2009/10 and 2010/11.

2 Cross-national student enrolment tables

2.1 Head counts by qualification type and fields of study

The tables in this section are based on the definitions and discussions of terms and categories in Sections 3 and 4. It should be noted that the occasional (or non-degree) students reported by Cape Town and Nelson Mandela are not included in the main rows of the head count tables.

The qualification types in the first column of Table 16 are those into which all the qualifications offered by the universities are clustered in their programme and qualification mixes (PQMs). The table summarises the head count enrolments of the nine participating universities by these qualification types, and permits comparisons to be made across and within categories.

Table 17 shows how head count student enrolments were distributed between the qualification categories over the three academic years recorded. The table shows that these nine universities have large commitments to undergraduate studies. In six of

the nine, undergraduates were more than 90% of the student enrolments, and in two between 80% and 86%. Only one had an undergraduate proportion of about 70%.

Tables 18 and 19 move from a consideration of qualification types to that of fields of study categories. Table 18 places the head count enrolments of the nine universities into the four broad fields of study that form one of the bases of the CHET data framework.

Table 18 shows that the field of study shapes of the nine universities differ widely. Two have more than 60% of their enrolments in the fields of education plus social science and humanities, and one has a proportion of only 20%. The education plus social science and humanities proportions of three universities fall in the range 40% to 60%, and the remaining three fall in the range 30% to 40%.

Table 19 sets out enrolment data figures within the 20 first-order categories discussed in Part Two and Part Three. This table allows comparisons to be made across the nine universities of enrolments within the broad categories of science and technology and humanities and social science. The data are extracted from the programme and qualification mix templates provided by the universities

TABLE 16: Summary of head count enrolments by qualification type (thousands)

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL AVERAGES					
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
Undergraduate certificates	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.5	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.6	2.3	0.8	4.1	3.6	2.5
Undergraduate diplomas	2.5	2.4	2.3	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	3.6	4.6	2.4	0.5	0.6	0.5	2.6	3.5	9.1	9.4	10.6	19.0	21.3	21.7	
Undergraduate degrees	10.6	10.8	11.9	14.9	15.1	15.3	16.3	15.8	17.2	27.6	28.0	31.4	31.6	31.0	31.1	34.1	40.1	44.2	9.5	9.8	10.8	169.9	178.5	192.3
Postgraduate below masters	0.2	0.1	0.1	2.5	2.7	2.9	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	1.6	1.4	1.2	4.7	4.5	4.5
Masters	1.1	1.3	1.3	3.3	3.6	3.9	0.5	0.5	0.8	2.2	2.6	4.2	1.5	1.5	1.7	0.7	0.8	0.9	8.0	10.6	11.8	19.7	23.7	27.5
Doctors	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.1	1.1	1.2	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	2.3	2.7	3.0
TOTAL THOUSANDS	14.5	14.7	15.7	22.6	23.4	24.2	17.6	17.0	18.8	33.6	35.5	38.4	34.1	33.6	34.0	45.2	55.1	61.5	24.7	25.1	25.7	219.8	234.5	251.4

TABLE 17: Shape of head count student enrolments by qualification type

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL AVERAGES					
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
Undergraduate certificates	0%	0%	0%	3%	3%	3%	4%	3%	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	11%	9%	3%	2%	2%	1%	
Undergraduate diplomas	17%	16%	15%	1%	1%	1%	0%	0%	0%	11%	13%	6%	1%	2%	2%	6%	5%	37%	37%	41%	9%	9%	9%	
Undergraduate degrees	73%	74%	76%	66%	65%	63%	92%	93%	91%	82%	79%	82%	93%	92%	91%	85%	84%	38%	39%	42%	77%	76%	76%	
Postgraduate below masters	2%	1%	1%	11%	11%	12%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	6%	6%	5%	2%	2%	2%	
Masters	8%	9%	8%	15%	15%	16%	3%	3%	3%	7%	11%	4%	4%	5%	5%	19%	9%	6%	7%	7%	9%	10%	11%	
Doctors	0.4%	0.4%	0.3%	4.7%	4.7%	5.0%	0.3%	0.6%	0.7%	0.4%	0.7%	0.8%	1.2%	1.4%	1.7%	0.6%	0.5%	1.6%	1.7%	1.6%	1.1%	1.2%	1.2%	
TOTAL THOUSANDS	14.5	14.7	15.7	22.6	23.4	24.2	17.6	17.0	18.8	33.6	35.5	38.4	34.1	33.6	34.0	45.2	55.1	61.5	24.7	25.1	25.7	219.8	234.5	251.4

TABLE 18: Proportions of head count enrolment in broad fields of study (thousands)

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL AVERAGES					
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
SET: Science and technology	23%	22%	21%	42%	42%	44%	18%	19%	20%	24%	26%	21%	46%	44%	42%	30%	27%	33%	34%	34%	34%	32%	33%	31%
BUS: Business, economics	28%	28%	28%	26%	25%	24%	15%	16%	14%	10%	9%	13%	21%	35%	37%	24%	21%	31%	31%	35%	31%	21%	23%	22%
EDU: Education	16%	15%	15%	4%	5%	4%	46%	46%	45%	1%	1%	1%	6%	7%	7%	1%	18%	22%	19%	14%	14%	15%	13%	13%
HUM: Humanities & social sciences	34%	35%	36%	26%	28%	28%	21%	18%	21%	65%	64%	66%	32%	30%	32%	25%	34%	16%	17%	17%	17%	31%	31%	34%
TOTAL THOUSANDS	14.5	14.7	15.7	22.6	23.4	24.2	17.6	17.0	18.8	33.6	35.5	38.4	34.1	33.6	34.0	45.2	55.1	61.4	24.7	25.1	25.7	219.8	234.7	251.4

TABLE 19: Head count enrolments by fields of study (thousands)

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL TOTALS														
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11													
SUBTOTAL: Science & technology	3.3	3.2	3.3	9.8	10.1	10.7	3.2	3.3	3.7	9.3	9.9	10.7	8.1	9.1	7.9	12.0	12.3	12.7	3.6	4.1	4.2	12.9	16.8	16.3	7.7	8.4	8.7	70.0	77.1	78.2	8.4		
SET01: Agriculture, agriculture operations	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.7	0.8	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.4	1.3	1.4	0.2	0.3	0.2	1.1	1.2	1.4	0.9	1.1	1.1	5.6	6.1	6.4	1.1		
SET02: Architecture & built environment	0.5	0.4	0.4	1.1	1.0	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.1	1.2	1.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.8	2.4	2.7	1.4	1.5	1.4	6.3	7.0	6.6	1.5		
SET03: Computer & information science	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.8	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.6	3.7	3.7	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.5	0.6	0.7	1.1	1.4	1.6	7.9	8.6	9.4	1.4		
SET04: Engineering	0.5	0.5	0.6	3.0	3.0	3.6	1.7	1.8	1.9	3.6	3.6	4.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	1.4	1.7	2.1	1.4	1.5	1.5	2.3	2.5	2.7	1.9	2.0	1.9	16.0	16.9	18.5	2.0		
SET05: Health & clinical sciences	0.5	0.5	0.6	3.1	2.8	3.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.7	1.8	1.9	3.2	4.0	2.5	1.7	1.7	1.8	0.5	0.5	0.5	4.1	4.0	4.1	1.3	1.5	1.3	16.1	16.8	15.8	1.5		
SET06: Consumer sciences	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.4	0.5	0.4	0.1		
SET07: Life sciences	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	1.1	1.2	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.7	3.1	3.1	3.4	1.1	1.0	1.0	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.6	1.2	0.6	0.1	0.1	0.4	6.7	7.7	7.8	0.1		
SET08: Physical sciences	1.4	1.3	1.2	0.8	1.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.6	1.8	1.9	1.9	0.8	0.8	0.8	1.1	1.1	1.0	0.4	0.4	0.4	1.7	4.0	3.3	0.5	0.6	0.8	8.3	10.8	10.2	0.6		
SET09: Mathematics & statistics	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.7	0.8	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.2	2.5	2.7	2.9	0.0		
SET10: Military sciences	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	
SET00: 1st order distinctions not made	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.1		
SUBTOTAL: Business, economics	4.0	4.1	4.3	5.9	5.8	5.8	2.7	2.7	2.9	3.1	3.9	3.9	3.2	3.2	4.9	7.2	7.3	7.7	2.7	3.2	3.7	11.1	15.7	13.2	7.7	7.8	9.0	47.3	52.9	55.2	7.8		
SUBTOTAL: Education	2.3	2.2	2.4	0.9	1.1	1.0	8.1	7.9	8.5	1.2	1.5	1.7	0.4	0.4	0.3	5.7	4.7	3.7	0.0	0.1	0.1	9.9	8.6	11.0	5.3	4.6	3.6	33.8	31.0	32.3	4.6		
SUBTOTAL: Humanities	4.9	5.2	5.7	6.0	6.5	6.7	3.7	3.1	3.9	6.2	6.8	7.1	21.9	22.7	25.2	9.2	9.3	9.9	1.5	1.8	1.9	11.3	14.0	21.0	4.0	4.2	4.4	63.8	73.7	85.8	4.2		
HUM01: Visual & performing arts	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	1.3	1.3	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.8				0.3		
HUM02: Communication & Journalism	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.4	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.0	1.9	1.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.5				0.5	
HUM03: Languages & literature	2.0	2.1	2.2	1.1	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.1	0.3	1.0	1.2	1.2	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.0	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.1				0.1	
HUM04: Law	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.0	1.1	1.0	1.2	0.9	1.2	2.2	1.9	2.0	1.3	1.3	1.2	1.2	0.3	0.5	0.6	1.5	1.9	2.2	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.0					1.1		
HUM05: Philosophy, religion	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.2	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
HUM06: Psychology	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.9	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.7	0.6	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.5				0.5	
HUM07: Public management & services	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.5	0.5				0.5	
HUM08: Social sciences	2.2	2.3	2.5	1.9	2.1	2.0	1.8	1.5	1.7	1.8	2.1	2.0	4.8	4.8	4.8	5.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	8.7	10.1	10.0	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.7				0.7	
HUM00: 1st-order distinctions not made	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.6	0.6	0.0	0.6	0.6				0.6	
OVERALL TOTAL	14.5	14.7	15.7	22.6	23.4	24.2	17.6	17.0	18.8	19.6	21.2	23.4	33.6	35.5	38.4	34.1	33.6	34.0	7.8	9.3	9.9	45.2	55.1	61.4	24.7	25.1	25.7	219.8	234.7	251.4	25.1		

2.2 Head count enrolments by gender

Table 20 focuses on the issue of gender equity. The data are also extracted from the PQM-based data templates of the universities. It shows what shares female students had of the total head count student enrolments and of enrolments in key areas such as science and technology fields of study and doctoral enrolments.

Table 20 shows that female students had a more than 50% share of total enrolments in four of the nine participating universities. Only two had female student shares of around 45% in science and technology programmes and in doctoral programmes.

2.3 FTE student enrolments

The final table in this section moves away from head count to full-time equivalent (FTE) student enrolments. Section 8 defines FTE students, and outlines the formal way in which FTE calculations should be made. It then suggests that the actual method of calculation should be determined by each university. This method could include assuming that most full-time students follow all the courses required in a standard curriculum, and that most part-time students carry 50% of a full-time load. On these assumptions a full-time student would be equivalent to 1 FTE student, and a part-time student to 0.5 FTE students. Table 21 summarises the totals of FTE enrolled students on this assumption.

3 Cross-national graduate tables

A graduate is defined as a student who has satisfied all the requirements for the award of a qualification that appears in the institution's programme and qualification mix (PQM) schedule. A graduate total counts all graduates as units, regardless of whether they were registered as full-time or part-time students. The qualification type and fields of study categories used in graduate tables are the same as those used in student enrolment tables.

Table 22 extracts graduate totals from the data submissions of the nine participating universities by qualification type. The table summarises these totals by broad fields of study.

Ratios between graduates and head count enrolments will be used in Part Six to generate output performance measures for the nine universities.

TABLE 20: Proportions of female students in head count enrolments

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL AVERAGES											
	2008/09	2009/10	2009/10	2010/11	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2008/09	2009/10	2008/09	2009/10	2008/09	2009/10	2008/09	2009/10	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11								
Undergraduate certificates	69%	62%	78%	60%	70%	66%	32%	27%	39%					41%	38%	65%														
Undergraduate diplomas	61%	61%	61%	45%	50%	43%	19%	22%	34%					48%	53%	40%														
Undergraduate degrees	54%	55%	55%	51%	52%	52%	39%	39%	39%					40%	39%	39%														
Postgraduate below masters	72%	70%	75%	50%	52%	52%	18%	24%	25%																					
Masters	49%	48%	52%	45%	46%	46%	35%	37%	39%					35%	36%	37%														
Doctors	43%	39%	39%	44%	44%	45%	29%	29%	28%					23%	24%	27%														
AVERAGE ALL QUALIFICATIONS & FIELDS OF STUDY	55%	55%	56%	50%	51%	52%	38%	39%	43%	31%	32%	32%	40%	41%	39%	44%	44%	44%	56%	56%	56%	36%	36%	38%	54%	54%	54%	43%	43%	44%
SET: Science and technology	29%	30%	29%	44%	46%	45%	25%	21%	30%	24%	25%	25%	39%	40%	33%	34%	33%	32%	41%	45%	28%	29%	31%	36%	36%	40%	34%	34%	34%	
BUS: Business, economics	62%	62%	63%	43%	43%	45%	34%	38%	42%	30%	31%	31%	36%	38%	35%	42%	44%	46%	67%	63%	34%	35%	37%	59%	59%	57%	44%	45%	46%	
EDU: Education	60%	61%	61%	59%	70%	66%	40%	42%	45%	38%	40%	41%	50%	45%	50%	47%	48%	47%	66%	17%	36%	38%	37%	69%	70%	75%	46%	48%	47%	
HUM: Humanities & social sciences	63%	63%	63%	65%	63%	66%	51%	51%	52%	41%	41%	42%	42%	41%	41%	58%	58%	58%	71%	70%	45%	47%	47%	63%	64%	64%	50%	50%	50%	

TABLE 21: FTE enrolled student totals

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL TOTALS											
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11									
SET: Science and technology	3273	3148	3298	7757	7785	7925	2581	2618	2996	8753	9154	9639	5537	6216	5380	10888	11040	11344	3311	3773	3894	10347	13429	13044	5807	6583	7037	59053	63743	64627
BUS: Business, economics	2779	2913	3141	4316	4491	4523	2139	2142	2125	2229	2483	3260	3144	3163	4832	5403	5632	6039	2308	2726	3138	8854	12523	10532	4294	5356	5649	35465	41428	43238
EDU: Education	2139	2094	2289	901	923	937	646	6311	6794	994	1163	1321	19594	20323	22462	4569	3913	3072	7	34	45	7954	6988	8765	2660	2214	1893	98103	89088	100373
HUM: Humanities & social sciences	4816	5025	5467	5980	6440	6478	2951	2510	3100	4924	5461	5640		8318	8398	8888	1317	1583	1628	9040	11223	16806	5495	6866	4811					
TOTAL	13006	13167	14175	18954	19639	19843	14118	13582	15014	16899	18250	19859	28274	29702	32675	28977	28883	29343	6943	8114	8695	36194	44074	49146	18256	18840	19990	181620	194259	208138

TABLE 22: Summary of graduates by qualification type

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DARES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL TOTALS											
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11							
Undergraduate qualifications	2 340	2 355	2 329	3 125	3 267	3 408	5 911	5 508	4 179	1 400	1 519	1 450	5 883	5 994	6 370	10 052	10 252	7 855	1 595	1 743	2 251	6 016	6 919	7 774	3 967	4 250	4 161	40 289	41 807	39 777
Postgraduate below masters	160	120	68	1 704	1 735	1 874	110	167	129	0	0	0	0	0	0	53	48	16	24	27	23	47	101	54	733	757	667	2831	2 955	2 831
Masters	191	217	206	888	1 009	1 085	659	567	566	22	117	109	683	1 101	1 591	822	847	670	247	196	396	395	2 015	2 533	249	312	390	4146	6 381	7 546
Doctors	8	6	10	178	160	163	12	16	24	0	0	2	16	17	36	38	55	55	11	13	15	18	43	61	39	63	59	320	373	425
TOTAL	2 699	2 698	2 613	5 875	6 171	6 530	6 692	6 258	4 898	1 422	1 636	1 561	6 592	7 112	7 997	10 965	11 202	8 596	1 877	1 979	2 685	6 476	9 078	10 422	4 988	5 382	5 277	47 568	51 516	50 579

TABLE 23: Proportions of graduates in broad fields of study

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DARES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL AVERAGES													
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11									
SET: Science and technology	15%	15%	17%	36%	35%	36%	16%	15%	19%	24%	13%	21%	22%	24%	13%	24%	13%	21%	22%	22%	35%	44%	39%	39%	32%	34%	31%	32%	34%	27%	28%	28%
BUS: Business, economics	22%	26%	26%	30%	29%	27%	15%	15%	18%	55%	30%	55%	14%	11%	15%	19%	21%	18%	21%	40%	35%	42%	21%	29%	33%	26%	25%	34%	23%	24%	27%	
EDU: Education	23%	23%	18%	7%	7%	8%	48%	47%	42%	8%	6%	10%	2%	2%	2%	21%	18%	12%	0%	0%	1%	28%	20%	19%	26%	28%	17%	21%	19%	14%		
HUM: Humanities & social sciences	40%	36%	38%	27%	29%	29%	22%	21%	21%	12%	8%	13%	62%	64%	62%	27%	27%	30%	20%	21%	22%	28%	24%	26%	17%	14%	15%	30%	29%	31%		
TOTAL	2 699	2 698	2 613	5 481	5 875	6 171	6 683	6 246	4 879	3 019	3 310	3 186	6 592	7 112	7 997	10 965	11 208	8 598	1 878	2 018	2 685	6 476	9 078	10 422	4 568	4 987	5 381	49 174	53 221	52 174		

4 Cross-national academic staffing tables

4.1 Permanent academics by rank and gender

Section 3 of Part Three stressed that the focus in staff analyses would be on academics because they are a key input for the teaching and research activities of universities.

Table 24 gives data for permanent academic staff members only. It gives the totals of permanent academics employed by each university, and shows how the totals were distributed by gender and by rank category.

Table 25 shows how the subtotals for rank and gender were distributed at each university. Because of the central role played by academic staff in knowledge production, the proportions by rank will be used as input indicators when the knowledge performances of the university are assessed.

Table 26 shows what proportions of the permanent academic staff of the nine universities had as their highest qualification either doctoral or masters degrees or a qualification below masters level. These proportions will also serve as input performance indicators in Section 5.

4.2 FTE academics by fields of study

A full-time equivalent (FTE) employee is a staff member who works at the university on a *full-time* basis for the 12 months of the reporting year. The fields of study of FTE academic staff members are determined by the area of studies linked to the academic units in which they are employed.

Table 27 summarises the FTE academic staff totals of the nine universities.

5 Move to performance indicators

Indicators are a means of referring to the complex properties or states of a higher education institution, either at a specific point in time or as these properties and states change over time. Performance as well as descriptive indicators can be drawn out of the cross-national data tables in Section 14 above. A distinction must however be drawn between these two kinds of indicator.

Performance indicators must be linked to the goals or targets that a university is expected to achieve. These could be goals that the university has set for itself, or goals that form part of national higher education policies. Descriptive indicators are not linked to performance measurement. They normally describe properties or states that institutions happen to have, independently of institutional or national goals.

Statements could, in different contexts, serve as either descriptive or performance indicators. Some examples are these:

- If none of the universities concerned had policies about growing enrolment and graduate totals, then the three statements below would be descriptive indicators:
 - Eduardo Mondlane's head count enrolment grew from 19 600 in 2008/09 to 23 400 in 2010/11.
 - Mauritius' overall total of graduates increased from 1 879 in 2008/09 to 2 685 in 2010/11
 - Nairobi's total of masters graduates increased from 395 in 2008/09 to 2 533 in 2010/11.

- If the next three universities had policies on student and staff gender equity, then the statements below would be performance indicators:
 - Female students had, in 2011, a 45% share of Cape Town's doctoral enrolments.
 - 29% of Makerere's permanent academics in 2010/11 were female.
 - 46% of Nairobi's permanent academics in 2010/11 were female.
- If the two universities did not have explicit goals for the improvement of staff qualifications, then the final two statements would contain descriptive indicators:
 - In 2010/11 45% of Dar es Salaam's permanent academics had doctoral qualifications.
 - In 2010/11 17% of Eduardo Mondlane's permanent academics had doctoral qualifications.

Part Six of this manual deals only with performance indicators. It shows how the data collected under the CHET framework can, when linked to research publications, be used to establish a set of cross-national performance indicators. Because the collection of research publications is not part of the framework described in this manual, a brief summary of research publication data is offered in Part Five.

TABLE 24: Totals of permanent academics in each rank and gender category

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NARROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL TOTALS											
	2008/09	2009/10	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11								
Professors	48	55	52	199	190	214	50	53	48	10	10	11	59	63	62	70	70	69	10	12	12	111	112	110	76	72	70	633	637	648
Associate professors	61	67	84	176	171	215	79	83	78	53	53	64	244	246	259	115	115	118	50	52	58	223	229	222	66	73	72	1 067	1 089	1 170
Senior lecturers	213	209	196	255	261	301	188	154	154	150	188	158	445	456	486	167	173	163	68	64	60	295	300	297	149	143	142	1 910	1 948	1 957
Lecturers	380	422	432	251	283	318	123	128	127	523	530	502	110	108	127	355	375	375	134	142	155	532	558	582	223	232	240	2 641	2 758	2 858
Junior lecturers	0	0	0	4	3	4	237	264	309	449	482	582	0	70	124	395	440	482	0	0	0	127	134	171	20	19	23	1 232	1 412	1 675
Other	0	0	0	14	15	3	120	182	190	24	24	36	32	0	0	0	0	0	2	5	2	0	0	0	35	35	32	227	261	283
TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	712	753	764	900	923	1 055	777	864	906	1 209	1 287	1 333	890	943	1 058	1 102	1 153	1 207	264	275	287	1 288	1 333	1 382	599	574	579	7 711	8 105	8 571
Female academics	223	233	251	346	372	446	138	131	124	266	309	272	217	232	259	303	326	345	116	116	125	309	325	346	256	255	288	2 174	2 299	2 436
Male academics	489	520	513	554	551	609	639	733	786	863	978	1 061	673	711	799	799	827	862	148	159	162	979	1 008	1 036	313	319	311	5 457	5 806	6 139

TABLE 25: Proportions of permanent academics in each rank and gender category

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NARROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL AVERAGES											
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008	2009	2010	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11						
Professors	7%	7%	7%	22%	21%	20%	6%	6%	5%	1%	1%	1%	7%	6%	6%	6%	6%	6%	4%	4%	4%	8%	8%	8%	13%	13%	12%	8%	8%	8%
Associate professors	9%	9%	11%	20%	18%	20%	10%	10%	9%	4%	4%	5%	12%	11%	12%	10%	10%	10%	19%	19%	20%	17%	17%	16%	12%	13%	12%	14%	13%	14%
Senior lecturers	30%	28%	26%	28%	28%	29%	22%	19%	17%	12%	15%	12%	27%	26%	24%	15%	15%	14%	26%	23%	23%	14%	14%	21%	26%	25%	25%	24%	24%	23%
Lecturers	55%	56%	57%	28%	31%	30%	16%	15%	14%	43%	41%	38%	50%	48%	46%	32%	31%	31%	51%	52%	54%	41%	42%	42%	39%	40%	41%	34%	34%	33%
Junior lecturers	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	31%	31%	34%	37%	37%	42%	0%	7%	12%	36%	38%	40%	0%	0%	0%	10%	10%	12%	4%	3%	4%	16%	17%	20%
Other	0%	0%	0%	2%	2%	0%	15%	21%	21%	2%	2%	3%	4%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%	2%	1%	0%	0%	0%	6%	6%	6%	3%	3%	3%
TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
Female academics	31%	31%	33%	38%	40%	42%	19%	16%	13%	22%	24%	20%	24%	25%	24%	27%	28%	29%	44%	42%	44%	24%	24%	25%	45%	44%	46%	29%	28%	28%
Male academics	69%	69%	67%	62%	60%	58%	82%	84%	88%	78%	76%	80%	76%	75%	76%	73%	72%	71%	56%	58%	56%	76%	76%	75%	55%	56%	54%	71%	72%	72%

TABLE 26: Highest formal qualification of permanent academic staff

	BOTSWANA			CAPE TOWN			DAR ES SALAAM			EDUARDO MONDLANE			GHANA			MAKERERE			MAURITIUS			NAIROBI			NELSON MANDELA			OVERALL AVERAGES					
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11			
Doctoral degree	64%	65%	65%	58%	62%	63%	55%	48%	45%	5%	19%	17%	51%	50%	50%	40%	42%	43%	41%	41%	42%	44%	45%	46%	37%	38%	37%	37%	38%	37%	17%	17%	17%
Masters degree	36%	35%	35%	31%	29%	28%	30%	33%	33%	43%	41%	38%	43%	44%	44%	47%	46%	45%	50%	48%	48%	29%	29%	30%	37%	37%	39%	37%	39%	16%	16%	15%	15%
Below masters degree	0%	0%	0%	11%	9%	8%	15%	19%	22%	52%	40%	45%	6%	6%	6%	13%	12%	12%	9%	11%	10%	27%	26%	24%	26%	25%	24%	32%	32%	30%	30%	30%	30%
TOTAL	712	753	764	900	923	1 065	777	864	906	1 209	1 287	1 333	880	943	1 058	1 082	1 153	1 207	264	275	287	1 288	1 333	1 382	569	574	579	7 759	8 131	8 573	8 131	8 573	8 573

TABLE 27: FTE academic staff by fields of study

	BOTSWANA			CAPE TOWN			DAR ES SALAAM			EDUARDO MONDLANE			GHANA			MAKERERE			MAURITIUS			NAIROBI			NELSON MANDELA			OVERALL TOTALS						
	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2009	2010	2011	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11				
SET: Science and technology	349	355	421	638	705	847	342	411	410	784	859	965	572	600	655	606	585	625	161	182	189	816	840	871	253	266	311	4 520	4 803	5 285	4 520	4 803	5 285	
BUS: Business, economics	86	90	90	122	139	215	69	72	94	122	122	210	84	85	95	64	62	69	79	84	94	67	70	70	83	106	129	776	829	1 065	776	829	1 065	
EDU: Education	147	147	147	68	55	56	74	88	80	13	13	45				71	68	76	3	3	5	81	93	91	47	51	53							
HUM: Humanities & social sciences	216	221	222	319	330	405	292	293	322	290	283	346	332	334	361	222	206	222	65	77	85	324	330	350	288	253	162	2 921	2 958	3 113	2 921	2 958	3 113	
TOTAL	798	813	880	1 146	1 229	1 523	777	864	906	1 209	1 287	1 556	988	1 009	1 111	962	919	992	308	347	373	12 888	1 333	1 382	671	677	656	8 217	8 478	9 379	8 217	8 478	9 379	

PART FIVE

RESEARCH PUBLICATIONS

1 Research publication units

Three different categories of research publication are recognised in data reported in South Africa's higher education management information system. These are (a) published proceedings of research conferences, (b) research books, and (c) articles in research journals. The basic requirement for all three categories is that of review and approval by a panel of research specialists before publication.

Because research publications receive government funding subsidies, two further criteria are applied when research article outputs are reported in South Africa. The first is that the article must be published in a journal that appears on the list of research journals compiled and approved by the South African Department of Higher Education. The second requirement is that only one publication unit is allocated to each research article. If the authors of a research article are employed by different universities, then fractions of the unit available are assigned to the universities concerned.

In its analyses of research outputs, CHET has considered research articles only. It uses the arts and humanities, social science, and science-expanded citation indexes of the Institute of Scientific Information (ISI), and extracts from them any paper that contains at least one author whose address is that of one of the participating universities. The South African practice of allocating a single unit per research publication is not followed. If the authors of a research publication recorded on a citation index are employed by different universities, then full units will be assigned to each of the universities concerned. This implies, in the case of a South African university, that its CHET research article count could be higher than the count approved for government funding purposes by the national Department of Higher Education.

Table 28 lists the ISI-based the research publication units of the nine universities, using the broad fields of study categories employed earlier in this manual. These units will be included in measurements of the performances of the nine universities.

TABLE 28: Research publication units allocated to universities

	BOTSWANA		CAPE TOWN		DAR ES SALAAM		EDUARDO MONDLANE		GHANA		MAKERERE		MAURITIUS		NAIROBI		NELSON MANDELA		OVERALL TOTALS											
	2008/09	2009/10	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11								
SET: Science & technology	109	77	71	1076	1156	1255	75	82	80	37	46	39	92	105	146	220	308	354	26	37	50	157	166	187	83	132	98	486	643	689
BUS: Business, economics	4	7	2	38	31	40	4	1	2	1	1	2	8	6	5	3	5	5	2	6	3	2	6	3	6	9	13	13	26	24
EDU: Education	6	10	6	14	23	24	1	2	2	0	0	1				3	3	6	0	1	1	1	1	1	4	5	8	296	332	365
HUM: Humanities & social sciences	9	28	29	181	171	198	12	7	6	2	2	4	24	19	19	7	24	17	1	4	9	13	15	7	18	17	17			
TOTAL	128	122	108	1309	1381	1517	92	92	90	40	49	46	124	130	170	233	340	382	29	48	63	173	188	198	111	163	136	546	739	779

PART SIX

CROSS-NATIONAL PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

1 Main requirements for university performance measurement

CHET showed in its 2012 report *Cross-national Performance Indicators: A Case Study of Eight African Countries* that sets of performance indicators can be applied to a grouping of universities from a range of African countries. The report argued that two features were essential for cross-national performance measurements. The first was that a quantitative data system, which interprets and prepares data in standard ways, must be available to, and accepted by, all participating universities. The second feature is that a set of goals must be common to, and accepted by, the participating universities, and their performance must be measured relative to these goals.

CHET's 2012 report argued that the principle of performance being relative to goals could be satisfied if the most prominent (or flagship) university in a range of countries is identified, if the goals that are built into the mission and vision statements of each flagship university are extracted, and if these are then related to goals that should be embedded in their academic cores. The report describes this academic core as the inputs available for the delivery of teaching and research, and the research and teaching outputs that the university produces on basis of these inputs. Cross-national measurements of the performance of universities would be based on assessments of the extent to which they satisfy the goals embedded in their academic cores.

Their vision and mission statements show that each of the eight universities listed in Table 1 in subsection 1.2 of the Introduction aims:

- to have a high academic rating, which would make it a world-class university or at least a leading university in Africa;
- to be a centre for academic excellence;
- to engage in high-quality research and scholarship; and
- to deliver knowledge products which will enhance national and regional development needs.

Nine specific 'flagship' goals can be extracted from the broad vision and mission goals set out above. When these are related to the quantitative data presented and analysed in Parts Two to Five of this manual, they satisfy the requirement that performance must be linked to goals. The goals are summed up in Table 29 on page 43.

TABLE 29: Goals related to mission and vision statements of participating universities

GOALS	NOTES ON GOALS
Goal 1: Strong enrolments in science, engineering and technology (SET)	In African governments and foreign development agencies, there is a strong emphasis on SET as an important driver of development
Goal 2: Strong postgraduate enrolments	The knowledge economy demands increasing numbers of people with postgraduate qualifications
Goal 3: Favourable academic staff to student ratios	The academic workload should allow for the possibility of research and PhD supervision
Goal 4: High proportion of academic staff with doctoral degrees	There is a strong correlation between staff with doctorates and research outputs
Goal 5: High proportions of academics in senior ranks	Research requires the leadership of senior academics
Goal 6: High commitment of academic staff to doctoral supervision	A productive university requires trained and skilled research students
Goal 7: High graduation rates in SET fields	Universities must achieve high success rates in order to respond to the skills shortages in SET fields in the African labour market
Goal 8: High levels of doctoral graduates	Doctoral graduates are critical both for the future reproduction of the academic staff, and for the knowledge economy
Goal 9: High levels of knowledge production in the form of research publications	Academics must produce peer-reviewed research publications if the university is to participate in the global knowledge community

A further goal concerned with gender equity must be added to the list above:

TABLE 29 (a)

GOALS	NOTES ON GOALS
Goal 10: Gender equity in student enrolments and academic staff	Socio-economic development requires increased participation of female students and female academic staff in higher education

Subsection 1.2 refers to an additional South African university that has been added to the data analyses, even though it cannot be classified as a flagship university. This is Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University (NMMU), which has been included with the eight flagship universities because of the long ties it has had with CHET's data and performance indicator projects.

2 Linking performance goals to quantitative targets

CHET discussed in its 2012 report *Cross-national Performance Indicators: A Case Study of Eight African Countries* the question of how performance targets should be set for any cross-national grouping of universities. CHET recognises that this continues to be an issue that needs to be resolved as more work is done on its cross-national analyses.

Table 30 sets up the first link between the goals in Table 29 and the data that have been developed in earlier sections of the manual. The middle column in the table sets out the data that will serve as indicators of performance relative to the goals. These data are all three-year averages. The final column gives the sources of the data, which are all drawn from earlier subsections of the manual.

TABLE 30: Goals and indicators

GOALS	INDICATOR DATA: ALL 3-YEAR AVERAGES FOR 2008/9 TO 2010/11	SOURCES OF DATA IN MANUAL
Goal 1: Strong enrolments in science, engineering and technology (SET)	% of head count students enrolled in science & technology programmes	Table 18
Goal 2: Strong postgraduate enrolments	% of head count students enrolled in (a) masters and (b) doctoral programmes	Table 17
Goal 3: Favourable academic staff to student ratios	Ratio of FTE students to FTE academic staff in (a) SET and (b) BUS programmes	SET & BUS rows in Table 21 divided by SET & BUS rows in Table 27
Goal 4: High proportion of academic staff with doctoral degrees	% of academics with doctoral degrees.	Table 26
Goal 5: High proportions of academics in senior ranks	% of academics in ranks of professor or associate professor	Table 25
Goal 6: High commitment of academic staff to doctoral supervision	Ratios of doctoral enrolments to permanent academics	Table 16 divided by totals in Table 26
Goal 7: High graduation rates in SET fields	Ratio for 2008/9 to 2010/11 of total SET graduates to total SET enrolments	Table 16 divided by totals in Table 26
Goal 8: High levels of doctoral graduates	Ratio of doctoral graduates to permanent academics	Table 16 divided by totals in Table 26
Goal 9: High levels of research knowledge production	Ratio of research publications to permanent academics	Table 16 divided by totals in Table 26
Goal 10: Gender equity in student and academic staff	% of women in (a) academic staff and (b) head count student enrolments	Table 16 divided by totals in Table 26

The second link between the goals and indicator data are performance targets. Table 31 summarises a set of targets that CHET has developed in other of its performance indicator publications. Many of these are likely to appear again as targets when CHET and the participating universities move towards agreement on cross-national performance indicators and targets.

TABLE 31: Goals and targets for performance measurement

GOALS	TARGET	BASIS FOR TARGET
Goal 1: Strong enrolments in science, engineering and technology	40% of head count enrolments to be in SET programmes	40% gives a strong focus to SET enrolments, with BUS being limited to 30% and humanities and social sciences also limited to 30%
Goal 2: Strong postgraduate enrolments	12% of head count enrolments to be in masters and 3% in doctoral programmes	Having 3% of enrolments in doctoral programmes shows that the university has a strong commitment to postgraduate teaching. The 12% share for masters shows that the feeder links needed for doctoral programmes are in place
Goal 3: Favourable enrolled student to academic staff ratios	In SET, ratio to be at most 12 FTE students per FTE academic. In business and management (BUS), the ratio to be at most 30:1	These ratios indicate the extent to which the university is able to serve the teaching/learning needs of its students. 12:1 has been regarded as an appropriate ratio for laboratory-based disciplines and 30:1 as a maximum for disciplines involved in large-class teaching
Goal 4: High proportion of academic staff with doctoral degrees	At least 50% of permanent academic staff to have doctoral degrees	The research outputs of an institution are related to its proportions of academic staff with doctorates. An overall proportion of 50% should be the minimum expected
Goal 5: High proportions of academics in senior ranks	At least 30% of permanent academic staff to be professors or associate professors	A university with a low proportion of senior academics would have difficulty in providing research leadership. A 30% proportion of permanent staff at associate professor or professor level should be a minimum research input requirement
Goal 6: High commitment of academic staff to masters and doctoral supervision	6a: Ratio of doctors enrolments to total permanent academic staff to be at least 0.5 6b: Ratio of doctors enrolments to permanent academic staff with doctorates to be at least 1.0	Academics with doctoral qualifications should be able to supervise at least 1 doctoral student in an academic year. If account is taken all academic staff, this ratio can be dropped to 0.5
Goal 7: High graduation rates in SET fields	Ratio of total SET graduates to SET enrolments to be at least 20%	A ratio of graduates to enrolments can serve as a proxy for a throughput rate. A ratio of 20% implies that at least 60% of all students entering SET programmes will eventually graduate.
Goal 8: High levels of doctoral graduates	8a: Ratio of doctors graduates to total permanent academic staff to be at least 0.15 8b: Ratio of doctors enrolments to permanent academic staff with doctorates to be at least 0,25	Academics with doctoral qualifications should be able to produce 1 doctoral graduate every 4 academic years. If account is taken all academic staff, this expectation can be dropped to 0.15, or 1 graduate every 7 years
Goal 9: High levels of knowledge production in the form of research publications	9a: Ratio of research publications to total permanent academic staff to be at least 0.5 9b: Ratio of research publications to permanent academic staff with doctorates to be at least 1.0	Academics with doctoral qualifications should be able to produce 1 research publication in an academic year. If account is taken all academic staff, this ratio can be dropped to 0.5
Goal 10: Gender equity in student and academic staff	10a: At least 50% of head count students to be female 10b: At least 50% of permanent academics to be female	Access equity requires male and females to have equal shares of student enrolments and of academic staff posts

3 Relating institutional performance to targets and goals

Table 33 relates three-year indicator data averages to the goals and targets in Table 31. Because Cape Town's performance met 15 of the 16 targets in the table, it has been placed in the first row in Table 32, and the first column in Table 33. The other eight universities have been left in alphabetical order in both tables.

Table 32 summarises the institutional performance pictures for 2008/09 to 2010/11 in terms of the numbers of targets which each institution has met. The table divides the goals and their related targets into an input group (Goals 1 to 6), an output group (Goals 7 to 9), and an equity group (Goal 10).

TABLE 32: Summary of numbers of targets met by each university

	INPUT TARGETS MET (GOALS 1–6)	OUTPUT TARGETS MET (GOALS 7–9)	EQUITY TARGETS MET (GOAL 10)
	TOTAL INPUT TARGETS = 9	TOTAL OUTPUT TARGETS = 5	TOTAL EQUITY TARGETS = 2
Cape Town	9	5	1
Botswana	2	0	1
Dar es Salaam	2	1	0
Eduardo Mondlane	3	0	0
Ghana	1	0	0
Makerere	1	1	0
Mauritius	1	1	1
Nairobi	1	0	0
Nelson Mandela	2	2	1

Table 33 contains a concise set of cross-national performance indicators. These can serve at least two purposes. They could allow universities to compare their input, output and equity data to those of other universities in the group of nine. They could also point to areas that could be subjected to more detailed, drill-down analyses by institutional planners and information specialists. CHET's view is that the data that underpin the indicators can be mined in useful ways by the participating universities.

TABLE 33: Details of institutional performance relative to goals and targets

GOALS	TARGET	DATA AVERAGES FOR 2008/09 TO 2010/11								
		CAPE TOWN	BOTSWANA	DAR ES SALAAM	EDUARDO MONDLANE	GHANA	MAKERERE	MAURITIUS	NAIROBI	NELSON MANDELA
Goal 1: Strong enrolments in science, engineering and technology	40% of head count enrolments to be in SET programmes	43%	22%	19%	46%	24%	36%	44%	29%	34%
Goal 2: Strong postgraduate enrolments	12% of head count enrolments to be in masters programmes	15%	8%	3%	5%	8%	5%	9%	19%	7%
	3% of head count enrolments to be in doctoral programmes	5%	0%	1%	0%	1%	1%	1%	0%	2%
Goal 3: Favourable academic staff to student ratios	3a: In SET, ratio to be at most 12:1	11	9	7	11	13	18	21	15	23
	3b: In BUS, to be at most 30:1	30	34	28	18	45	88	32	154	51
Goal 4: High proportion of academic staff with doctoral degrees	At least 50% of permanent academic staff to have doctoral degrees	61%	65%	49%	14%	50%	42%	41%	45%	37%
Goal 5: High proportions of academics in senior ranks	At least 30% of permanent academic staff to be professors or associate professors	41%	16%	15%	5%	18%	16%	23%	25%	25%
Goal 6: High commitment of academic staff to doctoral supervision	6a: Ratio of doctors enrolments to TOTAL permanent academic staff to be at least 0.50	1.17	0.07	0.11	0.01	0.24	0.42	0.17	0.16	0.71
	6b: Ratio of doctors enrolments to permanent academic staff with DOCTORATES to be at least 1.0	1.92	0.12	0.22	0.10	0.47	1.01	0.42	0.35	1.91
Goal 7: High graduation rates in SET fields	Ratio of total SET graduates to SET enrolments to be at least 20%	22%	13%	29%	7%	19%	29%	21%	14%	20%
Goal 8: High levels of doctoral graduates	8a: Ratio of doctors graduates to TOTAL permanent academic staff to be at least 0.15	0.17	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.09
	8b: Ratio of doctors graduates to permanent academic staff with DOCTORATES to be at least 0.25	0.28	0.02	0.04	0.00	0.05	0.10	0.11	0.07	0.25
Goal 9: High levels of knowledge production in the form of research publications	9a: Ratio of research publications to TOTAL permanent academic staff to be at least 0.50	1.46	0.16	0.11	0.04	0.15	0.28	0.17	0.14	0.24
	9b: Ratio of research publications to permanent academic staff with DOCTORATES to be at least 1.0	2.39	0.25	0.22	0.26	0.29	0.66	0.41	0.31	0.64
Goal 10: Gender equity in student and academic staff	10a: At least 50% of head count students to be female	51%	55%	40%	32%	40%	44%	56%	37%	54%
	10b: At least 50% of permanent academics to be female	40%	32%	16%	22%	24%	28%	43%	24%	45%

PART SEVEN

CONCLUDING NOTES

Subsection 2.2 of the Introduction said that this manual had been designed with three interrelated purposes in mind:

- It functions as a ‘user manual’ for institutional staff members who have (a) to extract the basic data required by the CHET framework, (b) to respond to any queries that may arise from the initial submissions of data, and (c) to interpret the data for the institution’s management.
- It functions as a higher-level ‘user manual’ that offers institutional planners and analysts detailed explanations and examples of the kinds of data that can be extracted from the CHET framework.
- It also provides more general overviews of (a) the development of the CHET data framework, and (b) of the uses of the data in institutional and in cross-national performance measurement.

These aims of the manual were ambitious, and may well have expected the discussion to cover too much ground. If users and/or readers of the manual find that further explanations of concepts and examples are needed, they should contact CHET at one or both of the following e-mail addresses: *iabunting@pine-wood.co.za* and *ncloete@chet.org.za*

APPENDIX 1

FIELDS OF STUDY CLASSIFICATIONS

GROUP A: SCIENCE, ENGINEERING & TECHNOLOGY [SET]

SET000	NO FIRST- OR SECOND-ORDER DISTINCTIONS MADE
SET01	AGRICULTURE, AGRICULTURAL OPERATIONS AND RELATED SCIENCES
Set0100	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0101	Agricultural business, management and economics
Set0102	Agricultural science and production; including crop science and production, livestock science and production, aquaculture, dairy science and production, fishing and fisheries sciences, equine science, poultry science and production
Set0103	Applied horticulture and horticultural business services
Set0104	Forestry and wood sSciences
Set0105	Food science and technology
Set0106	Agriculture other: areas of study that do not fit into the above categories
SET02	ARCHITECTURE AND THE BUILT ENVIRONMENT
Set0200	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0201	City/urban, community and regional planning
Set0202	Building and construction site management, including project management
Set0203	Architecture and environmental design
Set0204	Environmental architecture and design
Set0205	Landscape architecture and design
Set0206	Quantity surveying
Set0207	Architecture and the built environment other
SET03	COMPUTER AND INFORMATION SCIENCES
Set0300	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0301	Computer sciences
Set0302	Information sciences
Set0303	Computer programming
Set0304	Data processing
Set0305	Computer software and media applications
Set0306	Management information systems and services
Set0307	Computer and information sciences other
SET04	ENGINEERING
Set0400	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0401	Aerospace and aeronautical engineering
Set0402	Agricultural and bio-engineering
Set0403	Biomedical/medical engineering
Set0404	Chemical engineering
Set0405	Civil engineering
Set0406	Computer engineering
Set0407	Electrical, electronics and communications engineering
Set0408	Environmental/environmental health engineering
Set0409	Materials engineering
Set0410	Mechanical and mechatronic engineering
Set0411	Metallurgical engineering
Set0412	Mining and mineral engineering

Set0413	Naval architecture and marine engineering
Set0414	Nuclear engineering
Set0415	Ocean engineering
Set0416	Petroleum engineering
Set0417	Systems engineering
Set0418	Polymer/plastics engineering
Set0419	Industrial engineering
Set0420	Surveying engineering
Set0421	Geological/geophysical engineering
Set0422	Engineering other
SET05	HEALTH PROFESSIONS AND RELATED CLINICAL SCIENCES
Set0500	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0501	Chiropractic
Set0502	Communications disorders sciences and services
Set0503	Dentistry and oral sciences
Set0504	Dental support services and allied professions
Set0505	Health and medical administrative services
Set0506	Medicine
Set0507	Medical clinical sciences
Set0508	Nursing
Set0509	Optometry
Set0510	Osteopathy
Set0511	Pharmacy, pharmaceutical sciences and administration
Set0512	Podiatry
Set0513	Public health
Set0514	Radiography
Set0515	Rehabilitation and therapeutic professions
Set0516	Veterinary medicine
Set0517	Veterinary biomedical and clinical sciences
Set0518	Dietetics and clinical nutrition services
Set0519	Medical ethics
Set0520	Health professions and related clinical science other
SET06	FAMILY ECOLOGY AND CONSUMER SCIENCES
Set0600	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0601	Family and consumer sciences
Set0602	Family and consumer economics and related studies
Set0603	Foods, nutrition and related services
Set0604	Housing and human environments
Set0605	Human development, family studies and related services
Set0606	Apparel and textiles
Set0607	Family ecology and consumer sciences other
SET07	LIFE SCIENCES
Set0700	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0701	Biology
Set0702	Biochemistry, biophysics and molecular biochemistry
Set0703	Botany
Set0704	Cellular biology
Set0705	Microbiological sciences and immunology
Set0706	Zoology, including entomology
Set0707	Genetics
Set0708	Physiology, pathology and related sciences
Set0709	Pharmacology and toxicology
Set0710	Biomathematics and bioinformatics
Set0711	Biotechnology
Set0712	Ecology and population biology
Set0713	Life sciences other

SET08	PHYSICAL SCIENCES
Set0800	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0801	Astronomy and astrophysics
Set0802	Atmospheric sciences and meteorology
Set0803	Chemistry
Set0804	Geography and cartography
Set0805	Geology and earth sciences
Set0806	Physics
Set0807	Environmental science
Set0808	Physical sciences other

SET09	MATHEMATICS AND STATISTICS
Set0900	Second-order distinctions not made
Set0901	Mathematics
Set0902	Applied mathematics
Set0903	Statistics
Set0904	Mathematics and statistics

SET10	MILITARY SCIENCES
Set1000	Second-order distinctions not made
Set1001	Defence organisation and resource management
Set1002	Military human resource management and development
Set1003	Military technology and applied physical science
Set1004	Military security studies
Set1005	Military professional development
Set1006	Military sciences other

GROUP B BUSINESS AND MANAGEMENT

BUS01	BUSINESS, ECONOMICS AND MANAGEMENT STUDIES
Bus0100	Second-order distinctions not made
Bus0101	Business administration, management and operations
Bus0102	Accounting and auditing
Bus0103	Economics
Bus0104	Entrepreneurial and small business operations
Bus0105	Finance and financial management services
Bus0106	Hospitality management, including tourism
Bus0107	Human resource management and services
Bus0108	Management sciences and quantitative methods, including Actuarial science
Bus0109	Marketing
Bus0110	Real estate
Bus0111	Taxation
Bus0112	Insurance
Bus0113	Business, economics and management studies other

GROUP C EDUCATION

EDU01	EDUCATION
Edu0100	Second-order distinctions not made
Edu0101	Primary education level, including specific subject areas
Edu0102	Secondary education level, including specific subject areas
Edu0103	Early childhood education
Edu0104	Post-school education, including adult and higher education
Edu0105	Educational/instructional media design
Edu0106	Educational assessment, evaluation and research
Edu0107	International and comparative education
Edu0108	Social and philosophical foundations of education, including curriculum studies
Edu0109	Special needs education
Edu0110	Counsellor education and guidance services
Edu0111	Education other

GROUP D HUMANITIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES**HUM000 NO FIRST- OR SECOND-ORDER DISTINCTIONS MADE****HUM01 VISUAL AND PERFORMING ARTS**

Hum0100	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0101	Dance
Hum0102	Design and applied arts; including graphic design, fashion design, interior design
Hum0103	Drama and theatre arts
Hum0104	Film, video and photographic arts
Hum0105	Fine and studio art, including art history and theory, drawing, painting, sculpture,
Hum0106	Music, including history and theory of music, composition, music performance
Hum0107	Visual and performing arts other

HUM02 COMMUNICATION, JOURNALISM AND RELATED STUDIES

Hum0200	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0201	Communication and media studies
Hum0202	Journalism
Hum0203	Radio, television and digital communication
Hum0204	Public relations, advertising and applied communication
Hum0205	Publishing
Hum0206	Communication, journalism and related studies other

HUM03 LANGUAGES, LINGUISTICS AND LITERATURE

Hum0300	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0301	Linguistics and comparative literature
Hum0302	Studies of the languages: including literature, composition, creative writing
Hum0303	Languages, linguistics and literature other

HUM04 LAW

Hum0400	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0401	International aspects of law
Hum0402	Perspectives on law, including legal history, theory of law, jurisprudence
Hum0403	Mercantile law
Hum0404	Public and private law
Hum0405	Law other

HUM05 PHILOSOPHY, RELIGION AND THEOLOGY

Hum0500	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0501	Philosophy
Hum0502	Religion
Hum0503	Theology
Hum0504	Philosophy, religion and theology other

HUM06 PSYCHOLOGY

Hum0600	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0601	Clinical psychology
Hum0602	Counselling psychology
Hum0603	Developmental and child psychology
Hum0604	Educational psychology
Hum0605	Industrial and organisational psychology
Hum0606	Psychometrics and applied psychological assessment
Hum0607	Social psychology
Hum0608	Psychology other

HUM07 PUBLIC MANAGEMENT AND SERVICES

Hum0700	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0701	Community organisation and advocacy
Hum0702	Public administration
Hum0703	Public policy analysis
Hum0704	Criminal justice and corrections
Hum0705	Public management and services other

Hum08:	SOCIAL SCIENCES
Hum0800	Second-order distinctions not made
Hum0801	Anthropology
Hum0802	Archaeology
Hum0803	History
Hum0804	Library science/librarianship, including archives and archival management
Hum0805	Museum studies
Hum0806	Political science and government
Hum0807	Sociology
Hum0808	Social work
Hum0809	Social science other

APPENDIX 2

PROGRAMME AND QUALIFICATION MIX (PQM) OF UNIVERSITY OF BOTSWANA

NOTE: The qualifications in the schedule were sorted in the following order

- First: by qualification type [columns 1 and 2];
- Then: by broad field within each qualification type, in the order
 1. science & technology;
 2. business & management,
 3. education,
 4. humanities & social science [column 3];
- Then: by first-order subject matter classification within each broad field [column 4];
- Finally: by second-order category within each first-order category [column 5]

UNIVERSITY OF BOTSWANA: PROGRAMME AND QUALIFICATION SCHEDULE

	QUALIFICATION TYPE	BROAD FIELD OF STUDIES	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION
Undergraduate certificates				
Certificate in Land Administration	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering
Certificate in Archives & Records Management	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Undergraduate diplomas				
Diploma in Mining Engineering	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering
Diploma in Mineral Engineering	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering
Diploma in Land Management	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering
Diploma in Statistics	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics
Diploma in Accounting & Business Studies	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0113: Business, economics other
Diploma in Special Education	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education
Diploma in Adult Education	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104: Post-school education
Diploma in Non-Governmental Organisation Management	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Bus0113: Business, economics other
Diploma in Law	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM04: Law	Hum0400: 2nd order distinctions not made
Diploma in Criminal Justice Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management and services	Hum0704: Criminal justice & corrections
Diploma in Defence & Strategic Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management and services	Hum0705: Public management and services other
Diploma in Archives & Records Management	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Diploma in Library and Information Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Diploma in Population Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other
Diploma in Social Work	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work
Diploma in Youth in Development Work	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other
Undergraduate degrees				
Bachelor of Science (General)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET00: General	SET000: No first- or second-order distinctions made
Bachelor of Science (Urban & Regional Planning)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0201: Urban & regional planning
Bachelor of Engineering (Construction Engineering and Management)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0202: Construction, building
Bachelor of Architecture	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other
Bachelor of Design (Design & Technology)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other
Bachelor of Design (Industrial Design)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other
Bachelor of Science (Computer Science)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences
Bachelor of Science (Computing with Finance)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences
Bachelor of Science (Information Technology)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences
Bachelor of Information Systems (Computer Information Systems)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences
Bachelor of Engineering (Civil Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0405: Civil engineering
Bachelor of Engineering (Electrical & Electronic Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0407: Electrical engineering
Bachelor of Engineering (Mechanical Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0410: Mechanical engineering
Bachelor of Engineering (Mineral Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering
Bachelor of Science (Mining Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering
Bachelor of Engineering (Industrial Engineering)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0419: Industrial engineering
Bachelor of Geomatics	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering
Bachelor of Land Management	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering
Bachelor of Medicine Bachelor of Surgery	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0507: Medical clinical sciences
Bachelor of Science (Medical Laboratory Sciences)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0507: Medical clinical sciences
Bachelor of Science (Cytotechnology and Histotechnology Sciences)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0507: Medical clinical sciences
Bachelor of Nursing Science (Completion)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing
Bachelor of Nursing Science (Generic)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing
Bachelor of Science (Environmental Health)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0513: Public health
Bachelor of Science (Geology)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0805: Geology
Bachelor of Science (Applied Geophysics)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics
Bachelor of Science (Physics with Meteorology)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics
Bachelor of Science (Radiation and Health Physics)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics
Bachelor of Science (Environmental Science)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Bachelor of Science (General)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0901: Mathematics
Bachelor of Science (Mathematics)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics
Bachelor of Business Administration (International Business)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management
Bachelor of Business Administration (Logistics & Supply Chain Management)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management
Bachelor of Business Administration (Management)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management
Bachelor of Accountancy	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0102: Accounting
Bachelor of Arts (Economics)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics
Bachelor of Business Administration (Entrepreneurship & Enterprise Development)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0104: Entrepreneurial and small business operations
Bachelor of Finance	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0105: Banking & finance
Bachelor of Business Administration (Tourism & Hospitality Management)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0106: Hospitality management
Bachelor of Business Administration (Marketing)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0109: Marketing
Bachelor of Science (Real Estate)	Undergraduate	Business & management	BUS01: Business and management	Bus0110: Real estate
Bachelor of Information Systems (Business Information Systems)	Undergraduate	Science & technology	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0113: Business, economics other
Bachelor of Education (Primary Education)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0101: Primary education
Bachelor of Education (Secondary Education)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Bachelor of Education (Science Education)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Bachelor of Education (Physical Education)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Bachelor of Education (Adult Education)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education
Bachelor of Education (Special Education)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education
Bachelor of Education (Counseling)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education
Bachelor of Education (Business)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Bachelor of Education (Educational Management)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Bachelor of Education (Family & Consumer Sciences)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other

	QUALIFICATION TYPE	BROAD FIELD OF STUDIES	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION
Bachelor of Education (Home Economics)	Undergraduate	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Bachelor of Fine Arts (Theatre Arts)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM01: Visual and performing arts	Hum0103: Drama and theatre arts
Bachelor of Arts (Media Studies)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication, media studies
Bachelor of Media Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication, media studies
Bachelor of Information Systems (Information Management)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences
Bachelor of Arts (Chinese Studies)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages, linguistics and literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Bachelor of Arts (Humanities)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages, linguistics and literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Bachelor of Laws	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM04: Law	Hum0402: Perspectives on law
Bachelor of Arts (Pastoral Studies)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM05: Philosophy, Religion and Theology	Hum0503: Theology
Bachelor of Psychology	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	Hum06: Psychology	Hum0608: Psychology other
Bachelor of Arts in Criminal Justice Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public Management and Services	Hum0704: Criminal justice & corrections
Bachelor of Arts (Library & Information Studies)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Bachelor of Library & Information Studies	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Bachelor of Social Work	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work
Bachelor of Arts (Social Sciences)	Undergraduate	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0800: Second-order distinctions not made
Postgraduates certificates & Diplomas				
Postgraduate Diploma in Statistics	Postgrad below Masters	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics
Postgraduate Certificate in Educational Management	Postgrad below Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Postgraduate Certificate in Higher Education for Knowledge Society	Postgrad below Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Postgraduate Certificate in Research Methodologies for Development	Postgrad below Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Postgraduate Diploma in Science, Research, Educational Management	Postgrad below Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Postgraduate Diploma in Education	Postgrad below Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Masters degrees				
MA (Professional) in Urban and Regional Planning	Masters	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0201: Urban & regional planning
Master in Project Management	Masters	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0202: Construction, building
Master of Philosophy (Built Environment)	Masters	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other
Master of Philosophy (Design)	Masters	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other
Master of Philosophy (Project Management)	Masters	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment
Master of Philosophy (Technology)	Masters	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0200: Second-order distinctions not made
Master of Science (Computer Science)	Masters	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences
Master of Science (Computer Information Systems)	Masters	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences
Master of Science (Civil Engineering)	Masters	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0405: Civil engineering
Master of Science (Electrical & Electronic Engineering)	Masters	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0407: Electrical engineering
Master of Science (Mechanical Engineering)	Masters	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0410: Mechanical engineering
Master of Philosophy (Engineering)	Masters	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0400: Second-order distinctions not made
Master of Medicine Master of Surgery	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Master of Medicine (Anaesthesia)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Master of Medicine (Emergency Medicine)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Master of Medicine (Family Medicine)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Master of Medicine (Internal Medicine)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Master of Medicine (Paediatrics & Adolescent Health)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Master of Medicine (Pathology)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine
Master of Nursing Science	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing
Master of Medicine (Public Health)	Masters	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0513: Public Health
Master of Philosophy (Food & Nutrition)	Masters	Science & technology	SET06: Family ecology and consumer sciences	Set0601: Family and consumer sciences
Master of Philosophy (Biological Sciences)	Masters	Science & technology	SET07: Life sciences	Set0701: Biology
Master of Philosophy (Applied Microbiology)	Masters	Science & technology	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology
Master of Science (Applied Microbiology)	Masters	Science & technology	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology
Master of Science (Chemistry)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry
Master of Philosophy (Chemistry)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry
Master of Science (Hydrogeology)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0805: Geology
Master of Science (Physics)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics
Master of Philosophy (Physics)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics
Master of Philosophy (Natural Resource Management)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Master of Science (Environmental Science)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Master of Philosophy (Environmental Science)	Masters	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Master of Science (Mathematics)	Masters	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0901: Mathematics
Master of Philosophy (Mathematics)	Masters	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0901: Mathematics
Master of Arts (Statistics)	Masters	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics
Master of Philosophy (Statistics)	Masters	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics
Executive Master of Business Administration	Masters	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management
Master of Business Administration	Masters	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management
Master of Philosophy (Business)	Masters	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management
Master of Arts (Applied Economics)	Masters	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics
Master of Arts (Economics)	Masters	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics
Master in Education (Primary Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0101: Primary education
Master in Education (Religious Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Master in Education (Research & Evaluation)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Master of Education (Mathematics & Science)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Master of Philosophy (Geography Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Master of Philosophy (Language Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Master of Philosophy (Mathematics & Science)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Master of Philosophy (Infant Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0103: Early childhood education
Master of Education (Adult Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education
Master in Education (Social Studies Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education
Master of Philosophy (Adult Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education

	QUALIFICATION TYPE	BROAD FIELD OF STUDIES	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Research & Evaluation)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Educational assessment & evaluation
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Curriculum & Instruction)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education
Master of Philosophy (Special Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special needs education
Master in Education (Special Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education
Master of Philosophy (Counselling & Human Services)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education
Master of Education	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0100 Second-order distinctions not made
Master of Education (Counselling & Human Services)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education
Master of Education (Curriculum & Instruction)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Education (Educational Management)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Education (Educational Management-Flexi Mode)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Education (Gender Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master in Education (Physical Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master in Science, Research and Educational Management	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Philosophy (Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0100 Second-order distinctions not made
Master of Philosophy (Exercise Science)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Philosophy (Physical Education & Counselling)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Philosophy (Social Studies Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Education (Languages Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Education (Languages & Social Sciences)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Educational Management)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Philosophy Educational Technology	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM05: Philosophy, religion and theology	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Philosophy (Sports & Recreation Management)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Philosophy (Gender Education)	Masters	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Master of Arts (African Language & Literature)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Master of Philosophy (African Languages & Literature)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Master of Arts (English)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Master of Philosophy (English)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Master of Laws	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM04: Law	Hum0400: Second-order distinctions not made
Master of Arts (Theology & Religious Education)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM05: Philosophy, Religion and Theology	Hum0503: Theology
Master of Philosophy (Theology & Religious Studies)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM05: Philosophy, Religion and Theology	Hum0503: Theology
Master of Public Administration	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration
Master of Public Administration (Environmental Resource Management)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration
Master of Public Administration (Human Resource Management)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration
Master of Public Administration (Local Government Management)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration
Master of Public Administration (Public Financial Management)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration
Master of Public Administration (Public Policy & Administration)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0703: Public policy analysis
Master of Arts (Defence & Strategic Studies)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management and services	Hum0705: Public management and services other
Master of Philosophy (History)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0803: History
Master of Arts (History)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0803: History
Master of Arts (Library & Information Studies)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Masters of Archives & Records Management	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Master of Philosophy (Library & Information Studies)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Master of Philosophy (Political Science)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science
Masters in Politics & International Relations	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science
Master of Philosophy (Sociology)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0807: Sociology
Master of Social Work	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work
Master of Arts (Development Studies)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other
Master of Arts (Population Studies)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other
Master of Development Practice	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other
Master of Philosophy (Population Studies)	Masters	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other
Doctors degrees				
Doctor of Philosophy (Built Environment)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other
Doctor of Philosophy (Design)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other
Doctor of Philosophy (Project Management)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment
Doctor of Philosophy (Computer Information Systems)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences
Doctor of Philosophy (Engineering)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0400: Second-order distinctions not made
Doctor of Philosophy (Technology)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET04: Engineering	Set0422: Engineering other
Doctor of Philosophy (Food & Nutrition)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET05: Health sciences	Set0518: Diets and clinical nutrition
Doctor of Philosophy (Biological Sciences)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET07: Life sciences	Set0701: Biology
Doctor of Philosophy (Applied Microbiology)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology
Doctor of Philosophy (Chemistry)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry
Doctor of Philosophy (Physics)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics
Doctor of Philosophy (Environmental Science)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Doctor of Philosophy (Natural Resource Management)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Doctor of Philosophy (Natural Resource Management)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences
Doctor of Philosophy (Statistics)	Doctors	Science & technology	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics
Doctor of Philosophy (Business)	Doctors	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management
Doctor of Philosophy (Economics)	Doctors	Business & management	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics
Doctor of Philosophy (Mathematics & Science)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education
Doctor of Philosophy (Adult Education)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Research & Evaluation)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Educational assessment & evaluation
Doctor of Philosophy (Educational Foundations)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Curriculum & Instruction)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Special Education)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Counselling & Human Services)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education

	QUALIFICATION TYPE	BROAD FIELD OF STUDIES	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Educational Management)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Gender Education)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Doctor of Philosophy (Language Education)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other
Doctor of Philosophy (Education)	Doctors	Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0100: Second-order distinctions not made
Doctor of Philosophy (African Languages & Literature)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Doctor of Philosophy (English)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages
Doctor of Philosophy (Public Administration)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration
Doctor of Philosophy (History)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0803: History
Doctor of Philosophy (Library & Information Studies)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science
Doctor of Philosophy (Politics & International Relations)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science
Doctor of Philosophy (Political Science)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science
Doctor of Philosophy (Sociology)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0807: Sociology
Doctor of Philosophy (Social Work)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work
Doctor of Philosophy (Population Studies)	Doctors	Humanities & social sciences	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other

APPENDIX 3

UNIVERSITY OF BOTSWANA: DETAILS OF ENROLMENTS AND GRADUATES

	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	ENROLMENTS: FULL-TIME			ENROLMENTS: PART-TIME			GRADUATES		
			2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
Undergraduate certificates											
Certificate in Land Administration	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering	0	0	23	0	0	0	0	0	23
Certificate in Archives & Records Management	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	13	13	2	0	0	0	11	5	2
Undergraduate diplomas											
Diploma in Mining Engineering	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering	74	78	97	0	0	0	14	22	23
Diploma in Mineral Engineering	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diploma in Land Management	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diploma in Statistics	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	75	72	79	0	0	0	12	8	9
Diploma in Accounting & Business Studies	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0113: Business, economics other	0	0	0	1833	1839	1766	248	300	272
Diploma in Special Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diploma in Adult Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0104: Post-school education	26	22	24	34	24	17	22	24	14
Diploma in Non-Governmental Organisation Management	EDU01: Education	Bus0113: Business, economics other	0	0	0	12	11	11	0	0	4
Diploma in Law	HUM04: Law	Hum0400: Second-order distinctions not made	117	109	53	0	0	0	41	43	30
Diploma in Criminal Justice Studies	HUM07: Public management and services	Hum0704: Criminal justice & corrections	49	39	40	0	0	0	16	17	17
Diploma in Defence & Strategic Studies	HUM07: Public management and services	Hum0705: Public management and services other	0	0	23	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diploma in Archives & Records Management	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	47	30	43	0	0	0	31	16	11
Diploma in Library and Information Studies	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	33	34	61	0	0	0	0	15	15
Diploma in Population Studies	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	65	50	42	0	0	0	23	29	13
Diploma in Social Work	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work	79	79	87	0	0	0	22	30	32
Diploma in Youth in Development Work	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	0	0	0	6	6	5	2	0	2
Undergraduate degrees											
Bachelor of Science (General)	SET00: General	Set000: No 1st or 2nd order distinctions made	1337	1209	1129	0	0	0	61	58	63
Bachelor of Science (Urban & Regional Planning)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0201: Urban & regional planning	43	42	47	0	0	0	12	8	14
Bachelor of Engineering (Construction Engineering & Management)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0202: Construction, building	90	77	80	0	0	0	14	14	19
Bachelor of Architecture	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other	90	77	80	0	0	0	8	9	13
Bachelor of Design (Design & Technology)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other	90	77	80	0	0	0	14	17	16
Bachelor of Design (Industrial Design)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other	90	77	80	0	0	0	4	15	6
Bachelor of Science (Computer Science)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences	76	61	107	0	0	0	24	20	4
Bachelor of Science (Computing with Finance)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Science (Information Technology)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Information Systems (Computer Information Systems)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences	62	43	31	0	0	0	16	18	7
Bachelor of Engineering (Civil Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0405: Civil engineering	110	115	103	0	0	0	20	26	12
Bachelor of Engineering (Electrical & Electronic Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0407: Electrical engineering	102	97	94	0	0	0	10	16	17
Bachelor of Engineering (Mechanical Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0410: Mechanical engineering	121	108	98	0	0	0	17	12	28
Bachelor of Engineering (Mineral Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Science (Mining Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0412: Mining and mineral engineering	42	41	28	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Engineering (Industrial Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0419: Industrial engineering	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Geomatics	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering	3	38	67	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Land Management	SET04: Engineering	Set0420: Surveying engineering	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Medicine Bachelor of Surgery	SET05: Health sciences	Set0507: Medical clinical sciences	0	36	83	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Science (Medical Laboratory Sciences)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0507: Medical clinical sciences	0	17	25	0	0	0	0	6	24
Bachelor of Science (Cytotechnology and Histotechnology Sciences)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0507: Medical clinical sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Nursing Science (Completion)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing	52	54	36	0	0	0	65	64	55
Bachelor of Nursing Science (Generic)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing	200	202	226	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Science (Environmental Health)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0513: Public health	56	68	85	0	0	0	8	4	12
Bachelor of Science (Geology)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0805: Geology	0	0	0	0	0	0	29	18	18
Bachelor of Science (Applied Geophysics)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Science (Physics with Meteorology)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Science (Radiation and Health Physics)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Science (Environmental Science)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	20	12
Bachelor of Science (Statistics)	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	3	1	0	0	0	2	2	0	2
Bachelor of Business Administration (International Business)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Business Administration (Logistics & Supply Chain Management)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Business Administration (Management)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	323	333	398	192	185	199	77	76	94

	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	ENROLMENTS: FULL-TIME			ENROLMENTS: PART-TIME			GRADUATES		
			2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
			Bachelor of Accountancy	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0102: Accounting	552	576	636	165	153	156
Bachelor of Arts (Economics)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	8	16
Bachelor of Business Administration (Entrepreneurship & Enterprise Development)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0104: Entrepreneurial and small business operations	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Finance	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0105: Banking & finance	189	212	228	67	84	94	47	47	41
Bachelor of Business Administration (Tourism & Hospitality Management)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0106: Hospitality management	52	72	90	0	0	0	0	13	19
Bachelor of Business Administration (Marketing)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0109: Marketing	247	270	320	48	42	53	48	47	41
Bachelor of Science (Real Estate)	BUS01: Business and Management	Bus0110: Real estate	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Information Systems (Business Information Systems)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0113: Business, economics other	143	170	201	0	0	0	15	33	25
Bachelor of Education (Primary Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0101: Primary education	214	194	161	0	0	0	53	65	51
Bachelor of Education (Secondary Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	73	76	99	0	0	0	26	26	36
Bachelor of Education (Science Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	352	295	322	0	0	0	71	25	41
Bachelor of Education (Physical Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	228	268	366	0	0	0	58	51	38
Bachelor of Education (Adult Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0104: Post-school education	141	117	126	0	0	0	49	44	26
Bachelor of Education (Special Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education	248	227	294	0	0	0	62	80	40
Bachelor of Education (Counselling)	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education	93	158	185	0	0	0	0	45	31
Bachelor of Education (Business)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	19	41	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Education (Educational Management)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	126	138	140	0	0	0	36	35	35
Bachelor of Education (Family & Consumer Sciences)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	69	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Education (Home economics)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	164	161	115	0	0	0	34	47	45
Bachelor of Fine Arts (Theatre Arts)	HUM01: Visual and Performing Arts	Hum0103: Drama and theatre arts	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Arts (Media Studies)	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication, media studies	0	0	44	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Media Studies	HUM02: Communication, journalism	Hum0201: Communication, media studies	115	110	129	0	0	0	27	21	24
Bachelor of Information Systems (Information Management)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences	105	89	116	0	0	0	19	17	19
Bachelor of Arts (Chinese Studies)	HUM03: Languages, Linguistics and Literature	Hum0302: Studies of Languages	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Arts (Humanities)	HUM00	HUM000: No 1st- or 2nd-order distinctions made	1944	2089	2205	0	0	0	467	355	342
Bachelor of Laws	HUM04: Law	Hum0400: 2nd-order distinctions not made	378	415	477	0	0	0	58	50	58
Bachelor of Arts (Pastoral Studies)	HUM05: Philosophy, Religion and Theology	Hum0503: Theology	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Psychology	HUM06: Psychology	Hum0608: Psychology other	13	14	15	0	0	0	7	6	7
Bachelor of Arts in Criminal Justice Studies	HUM07: Public Management and Services	Hum0704: Criminal justice & corrections	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
Bachelor of Arts (Library & Information Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	18	38	36	0	0	0	34	10	14
Bachelor of Library & Information Studies	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	101	85	119	0	0	0	0	31	33
Bachelor of Social Work	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work	291	286	303	0	0	0	57	75	90
Bachelor of Arts (Social Sciences)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0800: 2nd-order distinctions not made	1285	1366	1479	0	0	0	207	208	234
Postgraduates certificates & diplomas											
Postgraduate Diploma in Statistics	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	2	1	0	1	0	2	0	0	0
Postgraduate Certificate in Educational Management	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Postgraduate Certificate in Higher Education for Knowledge Society	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Postgraduate Certificate in Research Methodologies for Development	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Postgraduate Diploma in Science, Research, Educational Management	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Postgraduate Diploma in Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	236	137	81	0	0	0	160	120	68
Masters degrees											
Master (Professional) in Urban and Regional Planning	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0201: Urban & regional planning	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master in Project Management	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0202: Construction, building	6	3	2	72	54	46	1	4	4
Master of Philosophy (Built Environment)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Design)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Project Management)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Technology)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0200: 2nd-order distinctions not made	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Science (Computer Science)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0301: Computer sciences	5	10	13	3	6	3	1	1	1
Master of Science (Computer Information Systems)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences	3	16	12	14	18	17	0	2	0
Master of Science (Civil Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0405: Civil engineering	8	6	3	4	13	15	0	1	2
Master of Science (Electrical & Electronic Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0407: Electrical engineering	15	10	8	8	14	9	3	1	1
Master of Science (Mechanical Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0410: Mechanical engineering	3	3	3	8	6	8	0	1	0
Master of Philosophy (Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0400: 2nd-order distinctions not made	0	1	1	0	1	6	0	0	0
Master of Medicine Master of Surgery	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Medicine (Anaesthesia)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Medicine (Emergency Medicine)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Medicine (Family Medicine)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Medicine (Internal Medicine)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Medicine (Paediatrics & Adolescent Health)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Medicine (Pathology)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0506: Medicine	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Nursing Science	SET05: Health sciences	Set0508: Nursing	8	8	9	24	29	26	2	3	2
Master of Medicine (Public Health)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0513: Public health	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Food & Nutrition)	SET06: Family Ecology and consumer sciences	Set0601: Family and consumer sciences	0	1	3	0	0	1	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Biological Sciences)	SET07: Life sciences	Set0701: Biology	0	4	9	0	6	6	3	1	4
Master of Science (Applied Microbiology)	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology	8	11	9	1	0	0	1	3	2
Master of Philosophy (Applied Microbiology)	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology	7	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Science (Chemistry)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry	12	12	12	0	0	0	4	1	4

	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	ENROLMENTS: FULL-TIME			ENROLMENTS: PART-TIME			GRADUATES		
			2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
			Master of Philosophy (Chemistry)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry	3	3	2	0	0	0
Master of Science (Hydrogeology)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0805: Geology	9	9	10	0	0	0	1	1	2
Master of Science (Physics)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	4	4	6	2	1	0	0	0	1
Master of Philosophy (Physics)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	0	2	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Natural Resource Management)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	0	6	6	0	3	1	0	0	0
Master of Science (Environmental Science)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	18	16	16	9	11	5	5	8	1
Master of Philosophy (Environmental Science)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	1	3	1	2	2	2	0	0	0
Master of Science (Mathematics)	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0901: Mathematics	6	5	9	4	5	6	3	1	7
Master of Philosophy (Mathematics)	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0901: Mathematics	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Arts (Statistics)	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	6	4	6	7	10	8	3	4	5
Master of Philosophy (Statistics)	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	0	0	3	0	0	1	0	0	0
Executive Master of Business Administration	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Business Administration	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	22	29	26	139	133	121	35	51	42
Master of Philosophy (Business)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0
Master of Arts (Applied Economics)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Arts (Economics)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics	20	21	31	0	0	0	11	8	10
Master in Education (Primary Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0101: Primary education	4	4	1	5	6	5	3	0	0
Master in Education (Religious Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	2	1	3	6	4	2	0	1	2
Master in Education (Research & Evaluation)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	11	22	24	23	33	43	7	9	4
Master of Education (Mathematics & Science)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	10	15	8	20	14	10	4	5	3
Master of Philosophy (Geography Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Language Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Mathematics & Science)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	0	1	0	2	1	2	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Infant Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0103: Early childhood education	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Master of Education (Adult Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education	8	12	6	18	13	18	7	4	0
Master in Education (Social Studies Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education	8	10	5	3	0	1	2	4	4
Master of Philosophy (Adult Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0104 Post-school education	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Research & Evaluation)	EDU01: Education	Edu0106: Educational assessment & evaluation	0	0	0	3	1	3	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Curriculum & Instruction)	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education	1	2	0	1	7	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Special Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special needs education	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	0	0
Master in Education (Special Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Counselling & Human Services)	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education	0	0	0	2	3	0	0	0	0
Master of Education	EDU01: Education	Edu0100 2nd-order distinctions not made	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Education (Counselling & Human Services)	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education	20	22	21	27	33	29	10	17	21
Master of Education (Curriculum & Instruction)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	7	9	6	12	14	11	7	1	2
Master of Education (Educational Management)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	26	24	13	29	29	36	10	14	3
Master of Education (Educational Management-Flexi Mode)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Education (Gender Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	1	3	9	13	19	15	1	1	7
Master in Education (Physical Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	7	9	11	28	24	15	4	1	3
Master in Science, Research and Educational Management	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0100: 2nd-order distinctions not made	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Exercise Science)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Physical Education & Counselling)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Social Studies Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0
Master of Education (Languages Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	2	3	3	4	5	4	0	1	1
Master of Education (Languages & Social Sciences)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Educational Management)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	1	0	3	4	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy Educational Technology	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Sports & Recreation Management)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Gender Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Theology & Religious Studies)	HUM05: Philosophy, religion and theology	Hum0503: Theology	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Arts (African Language & Literature)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	4	7	4	12	10	9	4	1	1
Master of Philosophy (African Languages & Literature)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Arts (English)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	16	15	10	9	9	7	5	4	4
Master of Philosophy (English)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	2	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Master of Laws	HUM04: Law	Hum0400: 2nd-order distinctions not made	5	2	2	7	11	15	2	0	3
Master of Arts (Theology & Religious Education)	HUM05: Philosophy, religion and theology	Hum0503: Theology	7	9	4	11	12	13	4	2	1
Master of Public Administration	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Public Administration (Environmental Resource Management)	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	2	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0
Master of Public Administration (Human Resource Management)	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	17	16	14	28	44	49	15	20	29
Master of Public Administration (Local Government Management)	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Public Administration (Public Financial Management)	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0
Master of Public Administration (Public Policy & Administration)	HUM07: Public management	Hum0703: Public policy analysis	2	4	3	1	0	0	1	3	3
Master of Arts (Defence & Strategic Studies)	HUM07: Public management and services	Hum0705: Public management and services other	0	0	14	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (History)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0803: History	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0
Master of Arts (History)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0803: History	2	8	5	3	3	3	0	1	3

	FIRST-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	SECOND-ORDER SUBJECT MATTER CLASSIFICATION	ENROLMENTS: FULL-TIME			ENROLMENTS: PART-TIME			GRADUATES		
			2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11	2008/09	2009/10	2010/11
			Master of Arts (Library & Information Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	10	11	7	20	19	15
Masters of Archives & Records Management	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	16	22	16	16	20	36	2	5	7
Master of Philosophy (Library & Information Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	1	1	0	3	3	2	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Political Science)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master's in Politics & International Relations	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science	16	14	19	8	22	32	0	2	0
Master of Philosophy (Sociology)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0807: Sociology	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Master of Social Work	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work	25	29	27	40	40	40	6	11	5
Master of Arts (Development Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	20	21	14	25	18	23	14	9	9
Master of Arts (Population Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	16	17	15	8	16	19	3	1	0
Master of Development Practice	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0
Master of Philosophy (Population Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctors degrees											
Doctor of Philosophy (Built Environment)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Design)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Project Management)	SET02: Architecture & built environment	Set0207: Architecture & built environment	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Computer Information Systems)	SET03: Computer & information sciences	Set0302: Information sciences	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Engineering)	SET04: Engineering	Set0400: 2nd-order distinctions not made	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Technology)	SET04: Engineering	Set0422: Engineering other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Food & Nutrition)	SET05: Health sciences	Set0518: Dietetics & clinical nutrition	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Biological Sciences)	SET07: Life sciences	Set0701: Biology	0	3	2	0	1	2	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Applied Microbiology)	SET07: Life sciences	Set0705: Microbiology	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Chemistry)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0803: Chemistry	5	5	7	0	0	0	0	0	3
Doctor of Philosophy (Physics)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0806: Physics	0	0	2	3	4	4	1	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Environmental Science)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	9	6	4	1	1	0	2	0	1
Doctor of Philosophy (Natural Resource Management)	SET08: Physical sciences	Set0807: Environmental sciences	0	3	0	0	2	1	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Statistics)	SET09: Maths & stats	Set0903: Statistics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Business)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0101: Business administration, management	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Economics)	BUS01: Business, economics & management	Bus0103: Economics	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Mathematics & Science)	EDU01: Education	Edu0102: Secondary education	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Adult Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0104: Post-school education	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Research & Evaluation)	EDU01: Education	Edu0106: Educational assessment & evaluation	1	1	1	2	4	4	0	1	3
Doctor of Philosophy (Educational Foundations)	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Curriculum & Instruction)	EDU01: Education	Edu0108: Foundations of education	1	2	0	0	0	1	0	1	0
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Special Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0109: Special education	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Counseling & Human Services)	EDU01: Education	Edu0110: Counsellor education	1	3	1	7	3	7	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Educational Management)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	1	1	0	3	3	4	0	1	0
Doctor of Philosophy Educational Foundations (Gender Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Language Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0111: Education other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Education)	EDU01: Education	Edu0100: 2nd-order distinctions not made	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (African Languages & Literature)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (English)	HUM03: Languages & literature	Hum0302: Studies of languages	0	0	2	1	0	1	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Public Administration)	HUM07: Public management	Hum0702: Public administration	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (History)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0803: History	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Library & Information Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0804: Library science	2	2	2	2	1	1	3	0	1
Doctor of Philosophy (Politics & International Relations)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Political Science)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0806: Political science	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Sociology)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0807: Sociology	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Social Work)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0808: Social work	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Doctor of Philosophy (Population Studies)	HUM08: Social sciences	Hum0809: Social science other	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
TOTALS			11 235	11 415	12 419	3 071	3 120	3 104	2 697	2 697	2 597

APPENDIX 4

MAKERERE UNIVERSITY: SUBMISSION OF ACADEMIC STAFFING DATA FOR 2010/11

ACADEMIC UNIT	SUBJECT AREA	PERMANENT ACADEMIC STAFF											FTE ACADEMIC STAFF		
		TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	BY RANK					BY GENDER		BY HIGHEST QUALIFICATION				TOTALS	
			Professors	Associate professors	Senior lecturers	Lecturers	Junior lecturers	Female	Male	Doctoral degrees	Masters degrees	Below masters degrees			Not reported
AGRICULTURE															
	Agricultural Economics & Agribusiness	16	0	4	0	8	4	6	10	8	8	0	0	14.3	
	Agricultural Engineering	12	0	0	2	3	7	2	10	1	9	2	0	10.9	
	Agricultural Extension/Education	12	0	1	1	6	4	5	7	6	6	0	0	11.9	
	Animal Science	12	1	1	3	3	4	3	9	4	8	0	0	11.2	
	Crop Science	18	2	2	7	4	3	5	13	11	7	0	0	18.8	
	Food Science and Technology	14	2	3	2	4	3	5	9	9	3	1	1	16.0	
	Soil Science	9	0	1	2	5	1	2	7	3	6	0	0	8.8	
	Subtotal for Agriculture	93	5	12	17	33	26	28	65	42	47	3	1	91.9	
ARTS															
	Geography	21	1	2	1	7	10	3	18	7	12	2	0	17.2	
	History	17	0	1	1	11	4	2	15	7	8	0	2	15.0	
	Languages	36	3	0	1	9	23	16	20	7	24	3	2	26.7	
	Literature	14	0	4	3	4	3	4	10	6	7	0	1	14.1	
	Mass Communication	10	0	2	0	2	6	4	6	1	6	3	0	7.9	
	Music, Dance and Drama	12	0	2	3	3	4	3	9	6	4	2	0	13.5	
	Philosophy	10	0	4	1	3	2	1	9	7	2	1	0	9.3	
	Religious Studies	12	0	0	1	10	1	3	9	8	3	0	1	11.5	
	Subtotal for Arts	132	4	15	11	49	53	36	96	49	66	11	6	115.2	
LIBRARY & INFORMATION SCIENCE															
	Information Science	6	2	1	1	2	1	5	3	2	1	1	5.3		
	Library Science	3	0	1	2	0	2	1	1	2	0	0	3.6		
	Records, Archives Management	3	1	0	1	1	1	2	1	2	0	0	4.0		
	Subtotal for Library & Information Science	12	3	0	2	4	3	4	8	5	6	0	1	12.9	
COMPUTING & INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY															
	Computer science	13	0	2	0	11	5	8	2	7	3	1	9.5		
	Information systems	11	0	1	0	10	5	6	2	8	1	0	8.0		
	Information technology	13	0	2	2	9	5	8	1	12	0	0	12.2		
	Network	11	1	1	1	8	3	8	2	5	3	1	8.1		
	Subtotal for Computing & Information Technology	48	0	1	6	38	18	30	7	32	7	2	37.8		
ECONOMICS & MANAGEMENT															
	Finance & accounting	16	0	0	1	15	2	14	1	13	2	0	12.5		
	Marketing & management	13	0	1	0	12	6	7	0	11	0	2	8.0		
	Development Economics	8	0	1	2	5	3	5	1	6	1	0	7.3		
	Economic Policy and Planning	12	1	2	4	5	3	9	5	6	0	1	10.8		
	Economic Theory and Analysis	8	0	1	4	3	0	8	0	8	0	0	9.3		
	Subtotal for Economics & Management	57	1	0	5	11	40	14	43	7	44	3	3	47.9	
FORESTRY & NATURE CONSERVATION															
	Community Forestry and Extension	7	1	0	2	3	2	5	3	3	1	0	6.5		
	Forest Biology, Ecosystem Management	14	1	4	3	3	1	13	7	5	1	1	15.1		
	Forest Management	10	0	1	0	4	5	3	7	2	6	2	0	8.3	
	Forest Products Engineering	6	1	0	0	1	4	2	4	1	4	1	0	6.9	
	Subtotal for Forestry & Nature Conservation	37	3	5	5	9	15	8	29	13	18	5	1	36.8	
STATISTICS & APPLIED ECONOMICS															
	Planning, Applied Statistics	11	0	1	2	4	4	1	10	5	5	1	0	11.2	
	Population Studies	12	1	0	2	2	7	5	7	4	4	2	2	11.2	
	Statistical Methods	10	0	0	1	3	6	3	7	1	7	2	0	8.8	
	Subtotal for Statistics & Applied Economics	33	1	1	5	9	17	9	24	10	16	5	2	31.2	
ADULT & CONTINUING EDUCATION															
	Adult and Communication Studies	10	0	1	1	8	3	7	2	6	2	0	6.3		
	Community Education, Extramural Studies	8	0	1	2	5	2	6	3	4	1	0	5.8		
	Distance Education	12	2	3	7	6	6	6	1	10	1	0	9.7		
	Subtotal for Adult & Continuing Education	30	0	0	4	6	20	11	19	6	20	4	0	21.8	
ENVIRONMENT															
	Environment	13	2	1	3	1	6	1	12	7	3	3	0	10.0	
	Subtotal for Environment	13	2	1	3	1	6	1	12	7	3	3	0	10.0	

AFRICAN UNIVERSITIES PERFORMANCE INDICATOR DATA MANUAL

ACADEMIC UNIT	SUBJECT AREA	PERMANENT ACADEMIC STAFF											FTE ACADEMIC STAFF		
		TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	BY RANK					BY GENDER		BY HIGHEST QUALIFICATION				TOTALS	
			Professors	Associate professors	Senior lecturers	Lecturers	Junior lecturers	Female	Male	Doctoral degrees	Masters degrees	Below masters degrees			Not reported
PSYCHOLOGY															
	Educational Psychology	7	0	0	1	2	4	4	3	1	3	1	2	6.4	
	Mental Health, Community Psychology	7	0	0	2	1	4	2	5	2	4	1	0	6.5	
	Organisational, Social Psychology	10	1	1	0	5	3	4	6	5	4	0	1	8.8	
	Subtotal for Psychology	24	1	1	3	8	11	10	14	8	11	2	3	21.7	
SOCIAL RESEARCH															
	Institute of Social Research	6	1		1	4		3	3	5		1		6.0	
	Subtotal for Social Research	6	1		1	4		3	3	5		1		6.0	
LAW															
	Commercial Law	10	1	0	0	1	8	3	7	0	8	0	2	7.1	
	Human Rights and Peace Center	11	1	0	1	3	6	4	7	0	8	0	3	9.3	
	Law and Jurisprudence	11	0	2	1	2	6	4	7	1	7	0	3	8.5	
	Public and Comparative Law	12	1	3	0	3	5	6	6	2	6	2	2	9.5	
	Subtotal for Law	44	3	5	2	9	25	17	27	3	29	2	10	34.4	
FINE ART															
	Industrial Arts and Design	13	0	1	2	4	6	5	8	3	10	0	0	10.9	
	Painting and Art History	12	1	0	2	6	3	4	8	1	7	1	3	10.8	
	Sculpture	10	0	1	2	3	4	5	5	2	7	0	1	8.3	
	Subtotal for Fine Art	35	1	2	6	13	13	14	21	6	24	1	4	30.0	
MEDICINE															
	Anaesthesia	2	0	0	0	2	0	1	1	0	1	1	0	2.3	
	Anatomy	9	0	1	3	2	3	0	9	1	3	2	3	7.8	
	Child Health, Development	6	0	1	1	1	3	2	4	2	3	0	1	5.1	
	Dentistry	12	0	0	3	6	3	3	9	3	7	1	1	11.1	
	E.N.T.	4	0	0	1	2	1	1	3	0	3	1	0	4.9	
	Family Medicine	7	0	0	0	4	3	0	7	0	4	2	1	6.1	
	Medical Illustration	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0.5	
	Medicine	20	4	3	2	8	3	6	14	4	11	3	2	23.3	
	Microbiology	10	1	2	1	4	2	2	8	4	5	1	0	10.3	
	Nursing	6	0	0	0	3	3	4	2	0	5	1	0	6.5	
	Obstetrics and Gynaecology	19	0	3	2	14	0	7	12	2	15	1	1	19.6	
	Ophthalmology	5	0	2	0	3	0	0	5	0	5	0	0	5.5	
	Orthopaedics	3	0	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	3	0	0	5.3	
	Pathology	5	2	1	0	1	1	1	4	1	3	1	0	7.3	
	Pediatrics and Child Health	13	1	4	2	4	2	7	6	0	10	2	1	14.0	
	Pharmacology and Therapeutics	9	1	2	0	1	5	3	6	2	6	0	1	8.5	
	Pharmacy	12	1	0	0	10	1	2	10	3	5	4	0	13.0	
	Physiology	9	0	0	1	3	5	3	6	0	4	3	2	8.0	
	Psychiatry	9	1	0	3	3	2	4	5	3	6	0	0	8.8	
	Radiology	7	1	0	0	3	3	1	6	0	4	2	1	7.4	
	Surgery	15	0	2	4	8	1	4	11	0	12	2	1	15.5	
	Subtotal for Medicine	183	12	21	23	85	42	51	132	25	116	27	15	190.8	
EDUCATION															
	Curriculum, Teaching and Media	10	0	0	3	4	3	6	4	5	4	1	0	9.4	
	Education Foundation and Management	12	0	0	1	6	5	3	9	4	7	1	0	9.5	
	Higher Education	10	1	0	1	8	0	1	9	7	1	0	2	10.0	
	Language Education	12	0	0	1	5	6	2	10	3	7	2	0	9.3	
	Science, Technical Education	10	0	1	4	4	1	2	8	7	2	1	0	13.0	
	Social Sciences, Arts Education	17	0	1	0	9	7	7	10	3	13	1	0	15.8	
	Subtotal for education	71	1	2	10	36	22	21	50	29	34	6	2	67.0	
PUBLIC HEALTH															
	Community Health & Behavioral Science	7	0	0	1	2	4	4	3	2	5	0	0	6.4	
	Disease Control, Environmental Health	12	1	1	2	3	5	3	9	2	9	1	0	9.8	
	Epidemiology, Biostatistics	12	0	2	3	3	4	3	9	4	6	0	2	11.1	
	Health Policy Planning, Management	7	0	1	0	4	2	1	6	5	0	1	1	6.0	
	Public Health	8	0	0	0	6	2	5	3	1	6	0	1	7.0	
	Subtotal for Public Health	46	1	4	6	18	17	16	30	14	26	2	4	40.3	
SCIENCE															
	Biochemistry	17	1	1	1	9	5	3	14	8	6	1	2	15.9	
	Botany	13	2	3	2	3	3	5	8	8	4	1	0	14.9	
	Chemistry	20	2	1	3	8	6	2	18	4	12	1	3	18.2	
	Sport sciences	2	0	0	0	0	2	2	0	0	2	0	0	3.7	
	Geology	12	0	2	2	3	5	5	7	6	6	0	0	9.8	
	Mathematics	18	2	1	1	7	7	3	15	5	10	2	1	16.5	
	Physics	15	3	1	1	5	5	1	14	10	3	1	1	15.5	
	Zoology	18	1	4	4	5	4	5	13	12	5	0	1	19.9	
	Subtotal for Science	115	11	13	14	40	37	26	89	53	48	6	8	114.4	
SOCIAL SCIENCES															
	Political Science, Public Admin	18	2	3	7	5	1	1	17	9	4	1	4	18.0	
	Social sciences	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1.0	
	Social Work, Social Admin	20	0	0	4	10	6	4	16	6	11	1	2	19.5	
	Sociology	19	2	1	6	5	5	4	15	7	10	2	0	17.9	
	Women and Gender Studies	18	1	1	5	5	6	14	4	9	7	1	1	17.3	
	Subtotal for Social Sciences	76	5	6	22	25	18	23	53	32	32	5	7	73.7	

ACADEMIC UNIT	SUBJECT AREA	PERMANENT ACADEMIC STAFF												FTE ACADEMIC STAFF	
		TOTAL PERMANENT ACADEMICS	BY RANK					BY GENDER		BY HIGHEST QUALIFICATION					TOTALS
			Professors	Associate professors	Senior lecturers	Lecturers	Junior lecturers	Female	Male	Doctoral degrees	Masters degrees	Below masters degrees	Not reported		
TECHNOLOGY															
	Architecture	14	0	2	1	6	5	5	9	6	6	1	1	14.1	
	Civil Engineering	20	2	0	4	5	9	2	18	3	14	1	2	18.4	
	Construction Economics & Management	6	0	1	0	0	5	2	4	1	2	2	1	6.2	
	Electrical Engineering	18	0	2	3	5	8	3	15	6	8	3	1	20.0	
	Engineering Mathematics	3	0	0	0	1	2	0	3	1	2	0	0	2.3	
	Mechanical Engineering	15	0	2	3	6	4	2	13	9	5	1	0	15.2	
	Surveying	11	0	0	2	5	4	2	9	2	5	1	3	11.7	
	Subtotal for Technology	87	2	7	13	28	37	16	71	28	42	9	8	87.9	
VETERINARY MEDICINE															
	Public Health & Preventative Medicine	8	1	1	0	1	5	3	5	2	4	2	0	6.1	
	Veterinary – Deans Office	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1.0	
	Veterinary Anatomy	8	1	1	3	3	0	3	5	4	4	0	0	9.2	
	Veterinary Medicine	11	1	1	4	2	3	3	8	2	7	1	1	11.2	
	Veterinary Parasitology, Microbiology	11	3	1	2	3	2	4	7	7	2	2	0	10.9	
	Veterinary Pathology	6	2	0	0	2	2	0	6	2	2	2	0	6.5	
	Veterinary Physiological Science	3	0	0	1	2	0	1	2	1	2	0	0	5.7	
	Veterinary Surgery	7	1	2	2	2	0	1	6	4	2	0	1	10.4	
	Wildlife, Animal Resources Management	12	2	1	0	1	8	5	7	3	7	1	1	10.2	
	Subtotal for Veterinary Medicine	67	11	7	13	16	20	21	46	25	31	8	3	71.2	
	OVERALL TOTALS	1209	68	103	171	407	460	347	862	374	645	110	80	1142.9	